

Sample Information

Name	Sample 5	Data File Path	C:\Users\NRC\OneDrive\Desktop\Data\meat flavor HS-MS\20.D
Sample ID		Acq. Time (Local)	1/10/2022 5:56:25 PM (UTC+02:00)
Instrument	GCMS	Method Path (Acq)	D:\MassHunter\GCMS\2\methods\Oils_Volatile.M
MS Type	Q	Version (Acq SW)	MassHunter GC/MS Acquisition 10.0.368 14-Feb-2019 Copyright © 1989-2018 Agilent Technologies, Inc.
Inj. Vol. (ul)	1	IRM Status	
Position	5	Method Path (DA)	C:\Users\NRC\OneDrive\Desktop\Data\meat flavor HS-MS\20.D\Results\Qual\Version4\Oils_Volatile.M
Plate Pos.		Target Source Path	
Operator		Result Summary	

Sample Chromatograms

Chromatogram Peaks

Peak	Start	RT	End	Height	Area	Area %	SNR
1	4.226	4.352	4.415	3163776	10166168	6.06	
2	19.188	19.281	19.452	2689628	12376650	7.37	
3	41.351	41.917	42.026	928194	14212521	8.47	
4	44.498	44.618	44.755	3524999	14542029	8.66	
5	57.900	58.093	58.236	5671860	31944029	19.03	
6	58.735	58.877	59.049	3112214	15027451	8.95	
7	64.350	64.611	64.725	588722	6464400	3.85	
8	64.725	64.897	65.113	1554501	14394715	8.57	
9	65.155	65.394	65.583	691289	5944665	3.54	
10	66.276	66.665	66.831	10743163	124496124	74.16	
11	66.968	67.014	67.140	814824	5878239	3.50	
12	67.437	67.575	67.803	1361949	11891367	7.08	
13	68.399	68.462	68.553	2244453	7382001	4.40	
14	68.553	68.822	68.994	3577790	37154840	22.13	
15	70.224	70.596	70.607	8056100	84018043	50.05	
16	70.607	70.613	70.710	8171595	40813293	24.31	
17	70.710	70.956	71.281	11157740	167882834	100.00	
18	71.645	71.729	71.874	1615783	8187098	4.88	
19	74.139	74.418	74.544	481797	7227815	4.31	

Chromatogram Peaks

Peak	Start	RT	End	Height	Area	Area %	SNR
1	4.226	4.357	4.398	1501537	4695082	35.68	
2	19.201	19.281	19.452	969524	4421990	33.60	
3	20.844	20.894	20.951	270970	818247	6.22	
4	25.095	25.403	25.535	133526	1288577	9.79	
5	31.706	31.783	31.852	348617	1170717	8.90	
6	41.350	41.911	42.043	216718	3294454	25.03	
7	44.498	44.618	44.784	2136190	8841918	67.19	
8	57.923	58.093	58.236	213870	1153332	8.76	
9	64.725	64.885	65.097	214151	1932403	14.68	
10	66.293	66.442	66.447	405908	1616220	12.28	
11	66.447	66.493	66.590	471694	3199336	24.31	
12	66.590	66.659	66.789	331370	2042542	15.52	
13	68.399	68.462	68.565	390167	1151887	8.75	
14	68.587	68.822	69.022	612126	5454542	41.45	
15	70.224	70.596	70.607	1270588	13160323	100.00	
16	70.607	70.613	70.750	1291567	6321317	48.03	
17	70.750	70.956	70.979	515704	5390997	40.96	
18	70.979	70.985	71.225	508259	1492876	11.34	

Chromatogram Peaks

Peak	Start	RT	End	Height	Area	Area %	SNR
19	71.639	71.735	71.894	290007	1364576	10.37	

Sample Spectra

+ Scan (rt: 4.283-4.363 min) Peak 1 from + BPC Scan ((2R,3R)-2-Methylbutane-1,3-diol; C5H12O2)

Spectrum Peaks

m/z	Z	Abund	Abund %	m/z (Calc)	Diff (ppm)	Ion Species	Formula	Ion Type
56.0300		9298	1.08					
60.0200		11364	1.32					
61.0300	1	607061	70.45					
62.0300	1	14617	1.70					
63.0100		120936	14.04					
70.0500		37123	4.31					
72.0700		9727	1.13					
73.0700	1	861646	100.00					
74.0600	1	57780	6.71					
75.0500	1	52766	6.12					
77.0300		13441	1.56					
88.0500		15558	1.81					
91.0400		20197	2.34					

Spectrum Identification Table

Best ID Source	Name	Formula	Species	m/z	Diff (ppm)	CAS	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (DB)	Score (MFG)	Lib/DB
Yes LibSearch	(2R,3R)-2-Methylbutane-1,3-diol	C5H12O2				997014-05-6	60.09	60.09			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	(2S,3R)-2-Methylbutane-1,3-diol	C5H12O2				997014-05-5	57.63	57.63			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	3,3,5,5-Tetrauteriomethoxycyclohexane	C7H10D4O				997021-68-1	52.05	52.05			W11N17main.L

Best Name	Formula	m/z (prec.)	CAS	RT (DB)	RT Diff	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (Fwd)	Score (Rev)	Lib/DB
Yes (2R,3R)-2-Methylbutane-1,3-diol	C5H12O2		997014-05-6	14.317		60.09	60.09			W11N17main.L

Observed Spectrum

Mirror Plot

Analysis Report

Library Spectrum

+ Scan (rt: 19.223-19.366 min) Peak 2 from + BPC Scan (Tolualdehyde [methylbenzaldehyde]; C8H8O)

Spectrum Peaks

m/z	Z	Abund	Abund %	m/z (Calc)	Diff (ppm)	Ion Species	Formula	Ion Type
51.0300		24782	5.18					
52.0300		7427	1.55					
53.0200		13801	2.89					
55.0200		10890	2.28					
59.0300		7701	1.61					
60.0200		11627	2.43					
60.9900		8473	1.77					
62.0100		18573	3.89					
63.0200		38328	8.02					
64.0300		11330	2.37					
65.0300		70354	14.72					
66.0300		16117	3.37					
74.0100		8409	1.76					
75.0200		8284	1.73					
77.0200		11266	2.36					
78.0300		5985	1.25					
89.0300		21941	4.59					
90.0300		6769	1.42					
91.0500		220385	46.11					
92.0500		24251	5.07					
94.0300		38352	8.02					
103.0400		6128	1.28					
105.0200		9380	1.96					
118.0300		7646	1.60					
119.0400		122383	25.61					
120.0500	1	477958	100.00					
121.0500	1	42391	8.87					

Spectrum Identification Table

Best ID Source	Name	Formula	Species	m/z	Diff (ppm)	CAS	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (DB)	Score (MFG)	Lib/DB
Yes LibSearch	Tolualdehyde [methylbenzaldehyde]	C8H8O			0-00-0		82.08	82.08			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	1,3,2-Benzodioxaborole	C6H5BO2			274-07-7		75.67	75.67			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Benethamine	C31H35N3O4S			997970-03-8		74.94	74.94			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	4,5-cyclopenteno-1,2-diazine	C7H8N2			6250-96-0		74.25	74.25			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Catecholborane	C6H5BO2			274-07-7		73.67	73.67			W11N17main.L

Best Name	Formula	m/z (prec.)	CAS	RT (DB)	RT Diff	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (Fwd)	Score (Rev)	Lib/DB
Yes Tolualdehyde [methylbenzaldehyde]	C8H8O		0-00-0			82.08	82.08			W11N17main.L

Observed Spectrum

Analysis Report

Mirror Plot

Library Spectrum

+ Scan (rt: 20.860-20.940 min) Peak 3 from + BPC Scan (E-myrtlenol; C₁₀H₁₈O)

Analysis Report

Spectrum Peaks

m/z	Z	Abund	Abund %	m/z (Calc)	Diff (ppm)	Ion Species	Formula	Ion Type
51.0200		5972	3.40					
52.0400		2349	1.34					
53.0400		17365	9.89					
54.0300		2498	1.42					
55.0600		14815	8.44					
56.0500		3340	1.90					
57.0600		5926	3.38					
59.0300		4446	2.53					
63.0000		3007	1.71					
65.0200		8200	4.67					
66.0100		2735	1.56					
67.0500		26421	15.05					
68.0500		33972	19.36					
69.0700	1	175504	100.00					
70.0700	1	14011	7.98					
71.0400	1	10892	6.21					
77.0300		10797	6.15					
78.0100		2403	1.37					
79.0400		12036	6.86					
80.0500		11612	6.62					
81.0500		10358	5.90					
82.0500		2682	1.53					
83.0400		7696	4.38					
84.0500		14452	8.23					
85.0600		3612	2.06					
91.0500		20872	11.89					
92.0400		9769	5.57					
93.0600		40938	23.33					
94.0500		8372	4.77					
95.0600		4867	2.77					
96.0700		4798	2.73					
97.0500		3274	1.87					
98.0400		2214	1.26					
105.0400		4262	2.43					
107.0600		5322	3.03					
109.0800		2021	1.15					
110.0600		2198	1.25					
111.0600		11093	6.32					
112.0500		2047	1.17					
119.0400		5958	3.39					
120.0400		19105	10.89					
121.0800	1	13984	7.97					
122.0500	1	1887	1.08					
123.1000	1	19471	11.09					
124.0700	1	2002	1.14					
136.1000		6067	3.46					
139.0900		4323	2.46					

Spectrum Identification Table

Best ID Source	Name	Formula	Species	m/z	Diff (ppm)	CAS	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (DB)	Score (MFG)	Lib/DB
Yes LibSearch	E-myrtanol	C10H18O				0-00-0	69.05	69.05			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Neryl Acetate	C12H22O2				0-00-0	65.22	65.22			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	3,7,11-Trimethyl-2,6,10-dodecatrien-1-ol	C15H24D2O				997283-78-4	62.48	62.48			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Isomyrcenylacetate	C12H18O2				80527-40-8	61.84	61.84			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	nerolidol Z and E	C15H26O				0-00-0	61.32	61.32			W11N17main.L

Best Name	Formula	m/z (prec.)	CAS	RT (DB)	RT Diff	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (Fwd)	Score (Rev)	Lib/DB
Yes E-myrtanol	C10H18O		0-00-0			69.05	69.05			W11N17main.L

Observed Spectrum

Mirror Plot

Analysis Report

Library Spectrum

+ Scan (rt: 25.146-25.437 min) Peak 4 from + BPC Scan (E-myrtlenol; C10H18O)

Spectrum Peaks

m/z	Z	Abund	Abund %	m/z (Calc)	Diff (ppm)	Ion Species	Formula	Ion Type
50.9900		1326	1.77					
51.0300		772	1.03					
52.0100		873	1.16					
53.0300		6029	8.04					
54.0400		1077	1.44					
55.0300		2754	3.67					
65.0200		2528	3.37					
67.0400		5074	6.76					
68.0500		1957	2.61					
69.0600	1	75013	100.00					
70.0600	1	4304	5.74					
77.0100		2489	3.32					
79.0300		2545	3.39					
81.0300		2001	2.67					
82.0400		6094	8.12					
83.0400		809	1.08					
85.0100		2167	2.89					
91.0300		4803	6.40					
93.0300		1104	1.47					
94.0000		891	1.19					
100.0300		13876	18.50					
105.0200		1091	1.45					
107.0400		1731	2.31					
110.9800		932	1.24					
118.9900		834	1.11					
120.0300		5707	7.61					
121.0100		1142	1.52					
122.0300		803	1.07					
122.0900		1961	2.61					
123.0900		10556	14.07					
124.0400		1857	2.48					
125.0400		4450	5.93					

Spectrum Identification Table

Best ID	Source	Name	Formula	Species	m/z	Diff (ppm)	CAS	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (DB)	Score (MFG)	Lib/DB
Yes	LibSearch	E-myrtlenol	C10H18O				0-00-0	51.70	51.70			W11N17main.L
No	LibSearch	Geranic acid	C10H16O2				459-80-3	51.57	51.57			W11N17main.L
No	LibSearch	2,6-Octadienoic acid, 3,7-dimethyl-, (E)-	C10H16O2				4698-08-2	51.12	51.12			W11N17main.L
No	LibSearch	2,6-Octadienoic acid, 3,7-dimethyl-, (Z)-	C10H16O2				4613-38-1	50.61	50.61			W11N17main.L
No	LibSearch	Neric acid	C10H16O2				4613-38-1	50.18	50.18			W11N17main.L

Best Name	Formula	m/z (prec.)	CAS	RT (DB)	RT Diff	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (Fwd)	Score (Rev)	Lib/DB
Yes E-myrtlenol	C10H18O		0-00-0			51.70	51.70			W11N17main.L

Observed Spectrum

Analysis Report

Mirror Plot

Library Spectrum

+ Scan (rt: 31.737-31.829 min) Peak 5 from + BPC Scan (Butylated hydroxy toluene; C15H24O)

Analysis Report

Spectrum Peaks

m/z	Z	Abund	Abund %	m/z (Calc)	Diff (ppm)	Ion Species	Formula	Ion Type
51.0200		2648	1.34					
53.0200		3988	2.02					
55.0500		9395	4.75					
57.0700		30187	15.27					
58.0300		2459	1.24					
65.0200		4272	2.16					
67.0300		9384	4.75					
69.0500		5080	2.57					
77.0300		8003	4.05					
78.0200		2278	1.15					
79.0500		5667	2.87					
81.0400		11474	5.80					
91.0400		14773	7.47					
93.0700		3325	1.68					
95.0600		8238	4.17					
103.0200		2733	1.38					
105.0500		14818	7.49					
115.0400		10548	5.33					
116.0500		3974	2.01					
117.0400		4765	2.41					
119.0600		9359	4.73					
120.0400		4176	2.11					
121.0500		7699	3.89					
127.0300		2622	1.33					
128.0500		8025	4.06					
129.0500		7489	3.79					
130.0600		3755	1.90					
131.0600		7663	3.88					
133.0700		7027	3.55					
135.0600		3605	1.82					
141.0600		5559	2.81					
142.0700		3966	2.01					
143.0700		2740	1.39					
145.0900	1	22750	11.51					
146.0700	1	3149	1.59					
147.0700	1	3208	1.62					
149.1000		2819	1.43					
157.0700		2801	1.42					
159.0800		2917	1.48					
161.0900		6706	3.39					
163.1200		3128	1.58					
177.1200		14189	7.18					
189.1200		7112	3.60					
205.1700	1	197719	100.00					
206.1700	1	30526	15.44					
207.1700	1	2720	1.38					
220.2000	1	48391	24.47					
221.1900	1	8044	4.07					

Spectrum Identification Table

Best ID Source	Name	Formula	Species	m/z	Diff (ppm)	CAS	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (DB)	Score (MFG)	Lib/DB
Yes LibSearch	Butylated hydroxy toluene	C15H24O				0-00-0	93.09	93.09			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	2,6-Di-tert-butyl-4-methyl-phenol	C15H24O				128-37-0	74.79	74.79			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	2,6-Di-tert-butyl-4-methyl-phenol	C15H24O				128-37-0	72.38	72.38			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Butylated Hydroxytoluene	C15H24O				128-37-0	71.49	71.49			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Butylated Hydroxytoluene	C15H24O				128-37-0	70.35	70.35			W11N17main.L

Best Name	Formula	m/z (prec.)	CAS	RT (DB)	RT Diff	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (Fwd)	Score (Rev)	Lib/DB
Yes Butylated hydroxy toluene	C15H24O		0-00-0			93.09	93.09			W11N17main.L

Observed Spectrum

Analysis Report

Mirror Plot

Library Spectrum

+ Scan (rt: 41.488-41.968 min) Peak 6 from + BPC Scan (p-Coumaric acid; C9H8O3)

Analysis Report

Spectrum Peaks

m/z	Z	Abund	Abund %	m/z (Calc)	Diff (ppm)	Ion Species	Formula	Ion Type
51.0200		6471	5.69					
53.0100		5461	4.81					
55.0100		3576	3.15					
59.0200		1272	1.12					
59.1100		1992	1.75					
60.9900		2103	1.85					
62.0000		5974	5.26					
63.0100		13716	12.07					
64.0100		4630	4.07					
65.0200		20708	18.23					
66.0100		2855	2.51					
67.0100		1349	1.19					
68.0000		2512	2.21					
69.0000		3347	2.95					
73.9100		1711	1.51					
74.9700		1196	1.05					
75.0100		1960	1.73					
77.0200		8117	7.14					
78.0200		1746	1.54					
79.0200		4490	3.95					
81.0300		1144	1.01					
82.0200		1298	1.14					
89.0300		13641	12.00					
90.0200		4414	3.88					
91.0400	1	29803	26.23					
92.0000		2073	1.82					
92.0500	1	1662	1.46					
94.0300		2603	2.29					
95.0000		1345	1.18					
101.0200		1635	1.44					
107.0300	1	15087	13.28					
108.0200	1	1895	1.67					
117.0200		1545	1.36					
118.0200		27379	24.10					
119.0300		29146	25.65					
120.0300		7797	6.86					
121.0300		2693	2.37					
123.0000		1770	1.56					
134.9900		1346	1.18					
135.0400		1815	1.60					
136.0300		3846	3.38					
146.0200		4446	3.91					
147.0300	1	49758	43.79					
148.0400	1	5065	4.46					
163.0400		42285	37.21					
164.0400	1	113626	100.00					
165.0400	1	11451	10.08					
166.0400	1	1328	1.17					

Spectrum Identification Table

Best ID Source	Name	Formula	Species	m/z	Diff (ppm)	CAS	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (DB)	Score (MFG)	Lib/DB
Yes LibSearch	p-Coumaric acid	C9H8O3				7400-08-0	76.46	76.46			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	p-Coumaric acid	C9H8O3				7400-08-0	74.55	74.55			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	p-Coumaric acid, trans	C9H8O3				501-98-4	73.29	73.29			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	2-Propenoic acid, 3-(4-hydroxyphenyl)-	C9H8O3				7400-08-0	72.89	72.89			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	p-Coumaric acid	C9H8O3				7400-08-0	72.48	72.48			W11N17main.L

Best Name	Formula	m/z (prec.)	CAS	RT (DB)	RT Diff	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (Fwd)	Score (Rev)	Lib/DB
Yes p-Coumaric acid	C9H8O3		7400-08-0	26.283		76.46	76.46			W11N17main.L

Observed Spectrum

Mirror Plot

Library Spectrum

+ Scan (rt: 44.549-44.658 min) Peak 7 from + BPC Scan (Benzoic acid, 2-hydroxy-, phenylmethyl ester; C14H12O3)

Spectrum Peaks

m/z	Z	Abund	Abund %	m/z (Calc)	Diff (ppm)	Ion Species	Formula	Ion Type
51.0200		21900	1.78					
53.0200		12463	1.01					
63.0200		36326	2.95					
64.0200		19813	1.61					
65.0300		144019	11.68					
77.0300		24085	1.95					
79.0400		12881	1.04					
89.0400		26646	2.16					
90.0500		12863	1.04					
91.0500	1	1232749	100.00					
92.0500	1	125079	10.15					
93.0200	1	23232	1.88					
120.0100		16858	1.37					
121.0100		38686	3.14					
228.0900	1	149934	12.16					
229.1000	1	23159	1.88					

Spectrum Identification Table

Best ID Source	Name	Formula	Species	m/z	Diff (ppm)	CAS	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (DB)	Score (MFG)	Lib/DB
Yes LibSearch	Benzoic acid, 2-hydroxy-, phenylmethyl ester	C14H12O3				118-58-1	72.23	72.23			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Benzoic acid, 2-hydroxy-, phenylmethyl ester	C14H12O3				118-58-1	70.68	70.68			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Benzoic acid, 2-hydroxy-, phenylmethyl ester	C14H12O3				118-58-1	70.48	70.48			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Benzoic acid, 2-hydroxy-, phenylmethyl ester	C14H12O3				118-58-1	69.71	69.71			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	4-Benzyloxybenzoic acid	C14H12O3				1486-51-7	68.34	68.34			W11N17main.L

Best Name	Formula	m/z (prec.)	CAS	RT (DB)	RT Diff	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (Fwd)	Score (Rev)	Lib/DB
Yes Benzoic acid, 2-hydroxy-, phenylmethyl ester	C14H12O3		118-58-1	32.567		72.23	72.23			W11N17main.L

Observed Spectrum

Mirror Plot

Library Spectrum

+ Scan (rt: 57.979-58.128 min)

Peak 8 from + BPC Scan (.alpha.-Pyrone, 4-methoxy-6-[2-(1-acetyl-p-pyridium chloride)-(E)-ethenyl]-; C₁₅H₁₄ClNO₄)

Analysis Report

Spectrum Peaks

m/z	Z	Abund	Abund %	m/z (Calc)	Diff (ppm)	Ion Species	Formula	Ion Type
51.0300		40837	33.72					
52.0300		20536	16.96					
53.0300		53830	44.45					
54.0300		8972	7.41					
55.0200		20262	16.73					
59.0100		26024	21.49					
63.0200		22653	18.71					
64.0200		12399	10.24					
65.0300		36902	30.47					
66.0300		13261	10.95					
67.0400		14917	12.32					
68.0200		10215	8.44					
69.0200		21898	18.08					
71.0100		13472	11.12					
77.0300		65401	54.01					
78.0400		29457	24.33					
79.0300		31237	25.79					
80.0200		11162	9.22					
81.0300		20515	16.94					
85.0200		10210	8.43					
89.0300		17758	14.66					
91.0500		48398	39.97					
92.0400		12258	10.12					
93.0200		11539	9.53					
94.0300		12676	10.47					
95.0200		14873	12.28					
97.0200		22158	18.30					
101.0100		8741	7.22					
102.0300		14614	12.07					
103.0400		27064	22.35					
104.0500		10684	8.82					
105.0400		45616	37.67					
106.0400		12319	10.17					
107.0200		20771	17.15					
108.0200		11197	9.25					
109.0200		9639	7.96					
115.0500		79849	65.94					
116.0500		20632	17.04					
117.0500		32302	26.67					
118.0500		10645	8.79					
119.0300		10981	9.07					
121.0200		20003	16.52					
122.0300		11212	9.26					
123.0300		19630	16.21					
127.0400		38381	31.69					
128.0500		74746	61.72					
129.0500		59548	49.17					
130.0600		12526	10.34					
131.0400		44055	36.38					
132.0400		23342	19.28					
133.0300		32318	26.69					
134.0300		12180	10.06					
135.0300		10730	8.86					
136.0400		47536	39.25					
139.0300	1	102548	84.68					
140.0400	1	11031	9.11					
145.0500		58202	48.06					
146.0500		15063	12.44					
147.0500		14335	11.84					
149.0200		11746	9.70					
150.0300		17047	14.08					
151.0300		9562	7.90					
155.0400		10962	9.05					
156.0600		12335	10.19					
157.0600		33315	27.51					
158.0600		12936	10.68					
159.0500		15472	12.78					
160.0500		121096	100.00					
161.0500		53197	43.93					
162.0500		13768	11.37					
164.0400		11334	9.36					
165.0500		65860	54.39					
173.0500		50804	41.95					
174.0600		25145	20.76					
175.0600		9660	7.98					
184.0500		17177	14.18					
185.0600		28134	23.23					
186.0600		10665	8.81					
187.0500		11611	9.59					
188.0600		14200	11.73					
189.0500		19441	16.05					
193.0600	1	91524	75.58					
194.0600	1	11203	9.25					
201.0600		117523	97.05					
202.0600	1	51584	42.60					
203.0700	1	12763	10.54					
212.0500		20681	17.08					
213.0600		19766	16.32					
215.0600		15187	12.54					
229.0600		106562	88.00					
230.0700	1	104185	86.04					
231.0700	1	19071	15.75					
240.0400		15530	12.82					

Analysis Report

Spectrum Peaks

m/z	Z	Abund	Abund %	m/z (Calc)	Diff (ppm)	Ion Species	Formula	Ion Type
244.0800		12846	10.61					
258.0600		48002	39.64					
259.0700		31156	25.73					
261.0900		36116	29.82					
262.0900		15163	12.52					
272.0700		20661	17.06					
290.0900		39195	32.37					

Spectrum Identification Table

Best ID Source	Name	Formula	Species	m/z	Diff (ppm)	CAS	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (DB)	Score (MFG)	Lib/DB
Yes LibSearch	.alpha.-Pyrone, 4-methoxy-6-[2-(1-acetyl-p-pyridium chloride)-(E)-ethenyl]-	C15H14ClNO4				997583-25-8	50.46	50.46			W11N17main.L

Best Name	Formula	m/z (prec.)	CAS	RT (DB)	RT Diff	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (Fwd)	Score (Rev)	Lib/DB
Yes .alpha.-Pyrone, 4-methoxy-6-[2-(1-acetyl-p-pyridium chloride)-(E)-ethenyl]-	C15H14ClNO4		997583-25-8			50.46	50.46			W11N17main.L

Observed Spectrum

Mirror Plot

Library Spectrum

+ Scan (rt: 64.748-65.017 min) Peak 9 from + BPC Scan (Noruns-12-ene; C29H48)

Analysis Report

Spectrum Peaks

m/z	Z	Abund	Abund %	m/z (Calc)	Diff (ppm)	Ion Species	Formula	Ion Type
53.0300		3945	3.20					
54.0300		1772	1.44					
55.0500		29176	23.63					
56.0600		4771	3.86					
57.0600		22712	18.40					
58.0300		1938	1.57					
59.9900		1744	1.41					
65.0100		2388	1.93					
67.0400		14431	11.69					
68.0400		4177	3.38					
69.0600		31663	25.65					
70.0600		4500	3.65					
71.0600		14082	11.41					
73.0100		3313	2.68					
77.0200		5955	4.82					
78.0100		1660	1.34					
79.0400		15179	12.30					
80.0400		4459	3.61					
81.0600		24572	19.90					
82.0600		6325	5.12					
83.0600		11684	9.46					
84.0600		2740	2.22					
85.0800		8677	7.03					
91.0500		16867	13.66					
92.0400		3469	2.81					
93.0600		18867	15.28					
94.0600		12130	9.83					
95.0700		27994	22.68					
96.0700		5468	4.43					
97.0700		9044	7.33					
98.0600		2394	1.94					
99.0800		3209	2.60					
105.0500		19097	15.47					
106.0500		4337	3.51					
107.0700		19347	15.67					
108.0700		7089	5.74					
109.0800		18629	15.09					
110.0700		3259	2.64					
111.0900		6620	5.36					
115.0200		2831	2.29					
117.0400		5122	4.15					
118.0400		1866	1.51					
119.0600		18586	15.06					
120.0700		7671	6.21					
121.0800		17293	14.01					
122.0800		7507	6.08					
123.1000		11094	8.99					
124.0800		2165	1.75					
125.0900		2043	1.65					
128.0400		2451	1.99					
129.0500		4248	3.44					
131.0600		6948	5.63					
132.0500		2211	1.79					
133.0800		13344	10.81					
134.0800		7385	5.98					
135.0900		16497	13.36					
136.1000		10139	8.21					
137.1100		10333	8.37					
138.1100		4173	3.38					
139.0900		2419	1.96					
143.0600		3132	2.54					
145.0800		7050	5.71					
146.0800		2404	1.95					
147.1000		12623	10.23					
148.1000		5660	4.58					
149.1200		7572	6.13					
150.1000		2497	2.02					
157.0800		2824	2.29					
159.1000		5419	4.39					
160.0900		1915	1.55					
161.1100		8914	7.22					
162.1100		4634	3.75					
163.1300		5059	4.10					
171.1000		2009	1.63					
173.1000		3606	2.92					
175.1400		12080	9.79					
176.1300		3497	2.83					
177.1400		3486	2.82					
185.0900		1698	1.38					
187.1400		3235	2.62					
189.1500		19696	15.95					
190.1600		8755	7.09					
191.1500		4911	3.98					
201.1300		2461	1.99					
203.1800	1	59014	47.80					
204.1800	1	11544	9.35					
205.1900	1	5503	4.46					
206.1900		1972	1.60					
207.1500		10721	8.68					
208.1500		2967	2.40					
213.1500		1624	1.32					
218.2100	1	123451	100.00					
219.2100	1	23220	18.81					

Analysis Report

Spectrum Peaks

m/z	Z	Abund	Abund %	m/z (Calc)	Diff (ppm)	Ion Species	Formula	Ion Type
220.2000	1	2448	1.98					
229.1800		2778	2.25					
231.1800		1783	1.44					
257.2200		3400	2.75					
281.1600		2277	1.84					
314.2700		1801	1.46					
426.4200		3648	2.96					

Spectrum Identification Table

Best ID Source	Name	Formula	Species	m/z	Diff (ppm)	CAS	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (DB)	Score (MFG)	Lib/DB
Yes LibSearch	Noruns-12-ene	C29H48				0-00-0	80.63	80.63			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Methyl commate A	C32H52O4				0-00-0	73.07	73.07			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	.beta.-Amyrin	C30H50O				559-70-6	67.51	67.51			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Olean-12-en-3-ol, acetate, (3.beta.)-	C32H52O2				1616-93-9	64.94	64.94			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Solanesol	C45H74O				0-00-0	64.79	64.79			W11N17main.L

Best Name	Formula	m/z (prec.)	CAS	RT (DB)	RT Diff	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (Fwd)	Score (Rev)	Lib/DB
Yes Noruns-12-ene	C29H48		0-00-0			80.63	80.63			W11N17main.L

Observed Spectrum

Mirror Plot

Library Spectrum

+ Scan (rt: 66.327-66.447 min) Peak 10 from + BPC Scan (Noruns-12-ene; C29H48)

Analysis Report

Spectrum Peaks

m/z	Z	Abund	Abund %	m/z (Calc)	Diff (ppm)	Ion Species	Formula	Ion Type
53.0300		7087	2.89					
55.0600		48921	19.92					
56.0500		6431	2.62					
57.0500		26304	10.71					
65.0200		3969	1.62					
67.0500		27108	11.04					
68.0500		7451	3.03					
69.0600		52274	21.29					
70.0600		5448	2.22					
71.0600		15122	6.16					
73.0200		5006	2.04					
77.0300		11535	4.70					
79.0400		27810	11.33					
80.0400		8134	3.31					
81.0600		45026	18.34					
82.0600		9738	3.97					
83.0700		17981	7.32					
84.0600		3906	1.59					
85.0800		7565	3.08					
91.0500		32140	13.09					
92.0500		6870	2.80					
93.0600		41382	16.85					
94.0600		16176	6.59					
95.0700		53824	21.92					
96.0600		9668	3.94					
97.0800		12349	5.03					
105.0500		38620	15.73					
106.0600		11697	4.76					
107.0700		43601	17.76					
108.0700		17119	6.97					
109.0900		41341	16.84					
110.0800		6547	2.67					
111.0900		9265	3.77					
115.0300		4944	2.01					
117.0500		9919	4.04					
118.0500		3507	1.43					
119.0700		46323	18.86					
120.0700		18372	7.48					
121.0800		40095	16.33					
122.0900		44960	18.31					
123.1000	1	34208	13.93					
124.1000	1	5054	2.06					
125.1000		4981	2.03					
128.0500		3491	1.42					
129.0600		7343	2.99					
131.0700		14292	5.82					
132.0700		5938	2.42					
133.0800		42481	17.30					
134.0900		26058	10.61					
135.1000		49424	20.13					
136.1100		36901	15.03					
137.1200		16257	6.62					
139.0800		3915	1.59					
142.0400		3226	1.31					
143.0700		6491	2.64					
145.0900		14979	6.10					
146.0900		5293	2.16					
147.1000		32062	13.06					
148.1100		21839	8.89					
149.1200		24268	9.88					
150.1200		6474	2.64					
151.1100		3150	1.28					
157.0900		5585	2.27					
159.1200		12033	4.90					
160.1100		4138	1.69					
161.1200		27891	11.36					
162.1300		14423	5.87					
163.1300		12583	5.12					
171.0900		4416	1.80					
173.1200		8645	3.52					
175.1400		19849	8.08					
176.1400		6311	2.57					
177.1400		6348	2.58					
187.1400		8015	3.26					
189.1600		49173	20.02					
190.1700		18866	7.68					
191.1500		7997	3.26					
201.1500		4585	1.87					
203.1800	1	52916	21.55					
204.1800	1	11480	4.67					
205.1800	1	6529	2.66					
206.1800	1	3527	1.44					
207.1600	1	34805	14.17					
208.1600	1	7975	3.25					
215.1800		3756	1.53					
217.2200		3814	1.55					
218.2200	1	245561	100.00					
219.2200	1	48313	19.67					
220.2100	1	5888	2.40					
229.1800		3279	1.34					
257.2200		5954	2.42					
271.2400		3131	1.28					
272.2400		4473	1.82					

Analysis Report

Spectrum Peaks

m/z	Z	Abund	Abund %	m/z (Calc)	Diff (ppm)	Ion Species	Formula	Ion Type
281.0700		3609	1.47					
365.3300		3516	1.43					
393.3600		4524	1.84					
408.3700		4021	1.64					
411.3900		5492	2.24					
426.4200	1	13683	5.57					
427.4000	1	4458	1.82					

Spectrum Identification Table

Best ID Source	Name	Formula	Species	m/z	Diff (ppm)	CAS	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (DB)	Score (MFG)	Lib/DB
Yes LibSearch	Noruns-12-ene	C29H48				0-00-0	80.86	80.86			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Methyl commate A	C32H52O4				0-00-0	74.56	74.56			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	.alpha.-Amyrin	C30H50O				638-95-9	69.52	69.52			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	.beta.-Amyrin	C30H50O				559-70-6	67.91	67.91			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	.alpha.-Amyrin	C30H50O				638-95-9	67.86	67.86			W11N17main.L

Best Name	Formula	m/z (prec.)	CAS	RT (DB)	RT Diff	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (Fwd)	Score (Rev)	Lib/DB
Yes Noruns-12-ene	C29H48		0-00-0			80.86	80.86			W11N17main.L

Observed Spectrum

Mirror Plot

Library Spectrum

+ Scan (rt: 66.447-66.590 min) Peak 11 from + BPC Scan (Noruns-12-ene; C29H48)

Analysis Report

Spectrum Peaks

m/z	Z	Abund	Abund %	m/z (Calc)	Diff (ppm)	Ion Species	Formula	Ion Type
53.0400		18116	4.57					
55.0600		112399	28.36					
56.0600		11976	3.02					
57.0500		45336	11.44					
65.0300		9066	2.29					
67.0400		75921	19.15					
68.0600		33760	8.52					
69.0700		148212	37.39					
70.0700		13983	3.53					
71.0600		30461	7.68					
77.0300		28935	7.30					
79.0500		75013	18.92					
80.0500		17975	4.53					
81.0600		119621	30.18					
82.0700		25371	6.40					
83.0700		40722	10.27					
85.0700		12017	3.03					
91.0500		81494	20.56					
92.0500		17291	4.36					
93.0600		118480	29.89					
94.0700		40197	10.14					
95.0800		147468	37.20					
96.0800		23354	5.89					
97.0800		26821	6.77					
105.0600		95091	23.99					
106.0600		28541	7.20					
107.0700		124939	31.52					
108.0800		52455	13.23					
109.0900		118873	29.99					
110.0900		19872	5.01					
111.0900		21744	5.49					
115.0400		9632	2.43					
117.0600		23364	5.89					
118.0600		8742	2.21					
119.0700		108762	27.44					
120.0800		42710	10.77					
121.0900		116286	29.34					
122.1000		90116	22.73					
123.1000	1	85599	21.60					
124.1000	1	11607	2.93					
125.1000	1	9819	2.48					
129.0700		14107	3.56					
131.0800		33804	8.53					
132.0700		14780	3.73					
133.0900		96019	24.22					
134.1000		60688	15.31					
135.1000		126531	31.92					
136.1100		75247	18.98					
137.1200		38108	9.61					
139.1000		9909	2.50					
143.0800		13240	3.34					
145.0900		37849	9.55					
146.1000		14174	3.58					
147.1100		84753	21.38					
148.1200		52884	13.34					
149.1200		63993	16.14					
150.1300		16651	4.20					
157.0900		11610	2.93					
159.1100		33214	8.38					
160.1200		13483	3.40					
161.1300		71981	18.16					
162.1400		33660	8.49					
163.1400		35394	8.93					
171.1100		9680	2.44					
173.1300		32318	8.15					
174.1400		9849	2.48					
175.1500		60901	15.36					
176.1500		17714	4.47					
177.1600		21076	5.32					
187.1500		29338	7.40					
188.1600		10888	2.75					
189.1700		122112	30.81					
190.1700		48148	12.15					
191.1700		31566	7.96					
201.1700		21055	5.31					
202.1800		11302	2.85					
203.1800		107714	27.17					
204.1800		33070	8.34					
205.1900		24192	6.10					
206.1900		16284	4.11					
207.1800	1	81031	20.44					
208.1800	1	20967	5.29					
215.1900		12419	3.13					
217.2200		14799	3.73					
218.2200	1	396380	100.00					
219.2200	1	79285	20.00					
220.2100	1	13634	3.44					
229.2000		13816	3.49					
231.2200		12058	3.04					
243.2100		8671	2.19					
257.2300		15952	4.02					
271.2500		13989	3.53					
272.2500		10706	2.70					

Analysis Report

Spectrum Peaks

m/z	Z	Abund	Abund %	m/z (Calc)	Diff (ppm)	Ion Species	Formula	Ion Type
286.2700		14898	3.76					
365.3400		18073	4.56					
393.3700		22233	5.61					
408.4000		20508	5.17					
411.3900		20533	5.18					
426.4200	1	39925	10.07					
427.4200	1	13299	3.36					

Spectrum Identification Table

Best ID Source	Name	Formula	Species	m/z	Diff (ppm)	CAS	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (DB)	Score (MFG)	Lib/DB
Yes LibSearch	Noruns-12-ene	C29H48				0-00-0	78.77	78.77			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Methyl commate E	C31H50O5				0-00-0	75.12	75.12			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Methyl commate A	C32H52O4				0-00-0	74.49	74.49			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Methyl commate B	C31H50O3				0-00-0	69.46	69.46			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Solanesol	C45H74O				0-00-0	68.48	68.48			W11N17main.L

Best Name	Formula	m/z (prec.)	CAS	RT (DB)	RT Diff	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (Fwd)	Score (Rev)	Lib/DB
Yes Noruns-12-ene	C29H48		0-00-0			78.77	78.77			W11N17main.L

Observed Spectrum

Mirror Plot

Library Spectrum

+ Scan (rt: 66.590-66.733 min) Peak 12 from + BPC Scan (Methyl commate B; C31H50O3)

Analysis Report

Spectrum Peaks

m/z	Z	Abund	Abund %	m/z (Calc)	Diff (ppm)	Ion Species	Formula	Ion Type
53.0400		29098	11.37					
55.0600		159097	62.15					
57.0600		47995	18.75					
67.0500		131310	51.30					
68.0600		78173	30.54					
69.0700	1	255976	100.00					
70.0700	1	20020	7.82					
71.0600		42828	16.73					
77.0400		45399	17.74					
79.0500		122314	47.78					
80.0600		25956	10.14					
81.0700		187687	73.32					
82.0700		43436	16.97					
83.0800		58765	22.96					
91.0500		125145	48.89					
92.0600		26524	10.36					
93.0700		193865	75.74					
94.0700		57919	22.63					
95.0800		235102	91.85					
96.0900		37656	14.71					
97.0900		40360	15.77					
105.0600		135985	53.12					
106.0700		39393	15.39					
107.0800		200969	78.51					
108.0900		87063	34.01					
109.0900		195095	76.22					
110.1000		34474	13.47					
111.1000		33012	12.90					
117.0600		33031	12.90					
119.0800		145552	56.86					
120.0900		56326	22.00					
121.1000		189397	73.99					
122.1000		80896	31.60					
123.1100	1	121019	47.28					
124.1100	1	16858	6.59					
129.0600		17661	6.90					
131.0800		47338	18.49					
132.0900		21309	8.32					
133.1000		118468	46.28					
134.1000		81533	31.85					
135.1100		179118	69.97					
136.1200		75051	29.32					
137.1300		53021	20.71					
139.1100		15828	6.18					
143.0900		16428	6.42					
145.1000		57835	22.59					
146.1100		22547	8.81					
147.1200		126734	49.51					
148.1200		69721	27.24					
149.1300		97085	37.93					
150.1400		24492	9.57					
159.1200		56804	22.19					
160.1200		25592	10.00					
161.1400		104627	40.87					
162.1400		40992	16.01					
163.1500		59462	23.23					
173.1400		68464	26.75					
174.1400		20701	8.09					
175.1500		103256	40.34					
176.1600		28429	11.11					
177.1600		40569	15.85					
187.1500		61218	23.92					
188.1600		23683	9.25					
189.1700		163635	63.93					
190.1800		65353	25.53					
191.1800	1	66499	25.98					
192.1800	1	16682	6.52					
201.1700		49884	19.49					
202.1800		25539	9.98					
203.1800		102477	40.03					
204.1900		56007	21.88					
205.2000		50857	19.87					
206.2000		36754	14.36					
207.1800		110407	43.13					
208.1900		33124	12.94					
215.1900		24922	9.74					
216.2000		18827	7.35					
217.2100		31358	12.25					
218.2200		131910	51.53					
219.2100		41351	16.15					
220.2000		19445	7.60					
229.2100		32638	12.75					
231.2200		22568	8.82					
234.2100		16185	6.32					
257.2400		24687	9.64					
271.2500		32815	12.82					
286.2800		41124	16.07					
297.2700		21918	8.56					
315.2800		24882	9.72					
316.2900		15885	6.21					
339.3200		23038	9.00					
365.3400		45024	17.59					
393.3700	1	67759	26.47					

Spectrum Peaks

m/z	Z	Abund	Abund %	m/z (Calc)	Diff (ppm)	Ion Species	Formula	Ion Type
394.3800	1	21612	8.44					
408.4000	1	51788	20.23					
409.4000	1	17771	6.94					
411.3900	1	51704	20.20					
412.4000	1	16442	6.42					
426.4100	1	65996	25.78					
427.4200	1	21392	8.36					

Spectrum Identification Table

Best ID Source	Name	Formula	Species	m/z	Diff (ppm)	CAS	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (DB)	Score (MFG)	Lib/DB
Yes LibSearch	Methyl commate B	C31H50O3				0-00-0	68.67	68.67			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Solanesol	C45H74O				0-00-0	68.60	68.60			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Methyl commate E	C31H50O5				0-00-0	66.09	66.09			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Geranyl linalool isomer	C20H34O				0-00-0	65.15	65.15			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Lupeol	C30H50O				545-47-1	63.25	63.25			W11N17main.L

Best Name	Formula	m/z (prec.)	CAS	RT (DB)	RT Diff	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (Fwd)	Score (Rev)	Lib/DB
Yes Methyl commate B	C31H50O3		0-00-0			68.67	68.67			W11N17main.L

Observed Spectrum

Mirror Plot

Library Spectrum

+ Scan (rt: 68.427-68.507 min) Peak 13 from + BPC Scan (Iron, tricarbonyl[N-(phenyl-2-pyridinylmethylene)benzenamine-N,N']-; C21H14FeN2O3)

Analysis Report

Spectrum Peaks

m/z	Z	Abund	Abund %	m/z (Calc)	Diff (ppm)	Ion Species	Formula	Ion Type
53.0300		3990	1.78					
54.0500		7034	3.14					
55.0600		70845	31.61					
56.0600		34205	15.26					
57.0700	1	224093	100.00					
58.0700	1	10522	4.70					
67.0400		16953	7.57					
68.0500		14840	6.62					
69.0700		62735	28.00					
70.0700		31370	14.00					
71.0800	1	167952	74.95					
72.0800	1	9606	4.29					
73.0300	1	4532	2.02					
77.0100		3095	1.38					
79.0400		6820	3.04					
80.0300		3103	1.38					
81.0500		17091	7.63					
82.0600		21022	9.38					
83.0800		53871	24.04					
84.0800		21476	9.58					
85.0900	1	127229	56.78					
86.0900	1	8514	3.80					
91.0300		7150	3.19					
93.0500		7475	3.34					
94.0500		3181	1.42					
95.0700		14893	6.65					
96.0700		14017	6.26					
97.0800		49216	21.96					
98.0900		16158	7.21					
99.1000	1	44821	20.00					
100.0800	1	4636	2.07					
105.0500		5414	2.42					
107.0600		5922	2.64					
108.0600		3087	1.38					
109.0800		10361	4.62					
110.0800		6816	3.04					
111.1000		26449	11.80					
112.1000		12075	5.39					
113.1100	1	27721	12.37					
114.1000	1	2583	1.15					
119.0500		5283	2.36					
120.0300		2637	1.18					
121.0700		5940	2.65					
122.0700		2333	1.04					
123.1000		6020	2.69					
124.0900		4430	1.98					
125.1100		12937	5.77					
126.1100		9318	4.16					
127.1300	1	19555	8.73					
128.0800	1	2275	1.02					
133.0600		4313	1.92					
135.0700		5225	2.33					
136.0800		2742	1.22					
137.1000		3299	1.47					
138.1200		3863	1.72					
139.1300		5324	2.38					
140.1400		7459	3.33					
141.1500		14228	6.35					
145.0700		2278	1.02					
147.0700		3942	1.76					
149.1000		2592	1.16					
153.1300		3007	1.34					
154.1600		6189	2.76					
155.1600		10696	4.77					
161.1000		2970	1.33					
168.1500		5048	2.25					
169.1800		8283	3.70					
175.1200		2282	1.02					
182.1900		4226	1.89					
183.2000		6349	2.83					
189.1400		5780	2.58					
191.1000		2662	1.19					
196.2100		3539	1.58					
197.2000		5532	2.47					
203.1600		2746	1.23					
204.1700		2921	1.30					
205.1900		4580	2.04					
207.0600		7549	3.37					
210.2100		3197	1.43					
211.2300		4470	1.99					
218.1900		2873	1.28					
224.2400		2416	1.08					
225.2600		3726	1.66					
239.2700		2651	1.18					
253.2000		3825	1.71					
267.2500		3032	1.35					
281.1200		2535	1.13					
281.2200		2580	1.15					
295.3200		2256	1.01					
408.4600		3109	1.39					

Analysis Report

Spectrum Identification Table

Best ID Source	Name	Formula	Species	m/z	Diff (ppm)	CAS	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (DB)	Score (MFG)	Lib/DB
Yes LibSearch	Iron, tricarbonyl[[N-(phenyl-2-pyridinylmethylene)benzenamine-N,N']-	C21H14FeN2O3				74764-11-7	70.99	70.99			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Trihexadecyl borate	C48H99B03				2665-11-4	69.77	69.77			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	1,1-Dideuterio-hexadecanyl methane sulfonate	C17H34D2O3S				56555-04-5	68.84	68.84			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	2-Azido-2,4,4,6,6,8,8-heptamethylnonane	C16H33N3				997443-71-2	66.85	66.85			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	2-Octadecyloxy-1,1,2,2-tetraetheroethanol	C20H38D4O2				56599-39-4	65.88	65.88			W11N17main.L

Best Name	Formula	m/z (prec.)	CAS	RT (DB)	RT Diff	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (Fwd)	Score (Rev)	Lib/DB
Yes Iron, tricarbonyl[[N-(phenyl-2-pyridinylmethylene)benzenamine-N,N']-	C21H14FeN2O3		74764-11-7			70.99	70.99			W11N17main.L

Observed Spectrum

Mirror Plot

Library Spectrum

+ Scan (rt: 68.668-68.931 min) Peak 14 from + BPC Scan (Noruns-12-ene; C29H48)

Analysis Report

Spectrum Peaks

m/z	Z	Abund	Abund %	m/z (Calc)	Diff (ppm)	Ion Species	Formula	Ion Type
53.0300		6501	1.94					
55.0600		49208	14.71					
56.0600		5567	1.66					
57.0700		18151	5.43					
58.0400		3725	1.11					
59.0400		4429	1.32					
65.0200		3726	1.11					
67.0400		25883	7.74					
68.0500		7140	2.13					
69.0700		69078	20.66					
70.0600		6251	1.87					
71.0600		13310	3.98					
73.0300		3729	1.11					
77.0300		11484	3.43					
79.0500		32247	9.64					
80.0500		9210	2.75					
81.0600		50520	15.11					
82.0600		9058	2.71					
83.0700		19012	5.69					
85.0700		7472	2.23					
91.0500		34056	10.18					
92.0500		7200	2.15					
93.0600		46387	13.87					
94.0700		28395	8.49					
95.0700		61546	18.40					
96.0700		10324	3.09					
97.0800		14630	4.37					
105.0600		43453	12.99					
106.0600		9925	2.97					
107.0700		47406	14.18					
108.0800		15569	4.66					
109.0800	1	44260	13.24					
110.0900	1	6040	1.81					
111.0900	1	12432	3.72					
115.0400		4648	1.39					
117.0500		10400	3.11					
119.0700		45732	13.68					
120.0800		15589	4.66					
121.0900		44135	13.20					
122.0900		17590	5.26					
123.1000		24827	7.42					
124.1000		4940	1.48					
125.1000		4145	1.24					
128.0400		4053	1.21					
129.0500		6786	2.03					
131.0700		14847	4.44					
132.0700		5225	1.56					
133.0800		34189	10.22					
134.0900		20298	6.07					
135.1000		42290	12.65					
136.1100		25325	7.57					
137.1300	1	25310	7.57					
138.1200	1	4224	1.26					
143.0700		6016	1.80					
145.1000		15075	4.51					
146.0900		6028	1.80					
147.1100		32286	9.65					
148.1100		14244	4.26					
149.1200		18519	5.54					
150.1200		5518	1.65					
157.0800		5154	1.54					
159.1200		12674	3.79					
160.1100		4362	1.30					
161.1300		24416	7.30					
162.1300		12226	3.66					
163.1300		12232	3.66					
171.1000		3870	1.16					
173.1200		9950	2.98					
175.1400		33793	10.11					
176.1500		9462	2.83					
177.1500		9415	2.82					
187.1400		9373	2.80					
188.1500		3796	1.14					
189.1600		61323	18.34					
190.1700		23099	6.91					
191.1700		12644	3.78					
201.1600		7570	2.26					
202.1700		5106	1.53					
203.1800	1	161216	48.21					
204.1900	1	33529	10.03					
205.2000	1	16837	5.03					
206.2100	1	4949	1.48					
207.0600		8057	2.41					
215.1800		6146	1.84					
216.1900		3710	1.11					
218.2200	1	334410	100.00					
219.2200	1	62709	18.75					
220.2100	1	5921	1.77					
229.2000		5709	1.71					
231.2100		4565	1.37					
243.2100		4083	1.22					
249.1800		3712	1.11					
255.2000		4802	1.44					

Analysis Report

Spectrum Peaks

m/z	Z	Abund	Abund %	m/z (Calc)	Diff (ppm)	Ion Species	Formula	Ion Type
257.2300		8637	2.58					
270.2400		3616	1.08					
271.2400		5025	1.50					
365.3500		4325	1.29					
393.3700		6138	1.84					
408.3700		4903	1.47					
468.4400		7178	2.15					

Spectrum Identification Table

Best ID Source	Name	Formula	Species	m/z	Diff (ppm)	CAS	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (DB)	Score (MFG)	Lib/DB
Yes LibSearch	Noruns-12-ene	C29H48				0-00-0	82.07	82.07			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Methyl commate A	C32H52O4				0-00-0	79.65	79.65			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Olean-12-en-3-ol, acetate, (3.beta.)-	C32H52O2				1616-93-9	72.15	72.15			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	12-Oleanen-3-yl acetate, (3.alpha.)-	C32H52O2				33055-28-6	66.60	66.60			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	.beta.-Amyrin	C30H50O				559-70-6	66.47	66.47			W11N17main.L

Best Name	Formula	m/z (prec.)	CAS	RT (DB)	RT Diff	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (Fwd)	Score (Rev)	Lib/DB
Yes Noruns-12-ene	C29H48		0-00-0			82.07	82.07			W11N17main.L

Observed Spectrum

Mirror Plot

Library Spectrum

+ Scan (rt: 70.321-70.607 min) Peak 15 from + BPC Scan (Noruns-12-ene; C29H48)

Analysis Report

Spectrum Peaks

m/z	Z	Abund	Abund %	m/z (Calc)	Diff (ppm)	Ion Species	Formula	Ion Type
53.0400		10776	1.42					
55.0600		84016	11.04					
56.0600		8011	1.05					
57.0600		21065	2.77					
67.0500		44509	5.85					
68.0600		9136	1.20					
69.0700	1	107933	14.18					
70.0700	1	8450	1.11					
71.0600	1	14261	1.87					
77.0300		21681	2.85					
79.0500		56962	7.48					
80.0600		13969	1.84					
81.0600		96134	12.63					
82.0700		14170	1.86					
83.0800		30804	4.05					
85.0700		9700	1.27					
91.0500		68761	9.03					
92.0500		13495	1.77					
93.0600		95250	12.52					
94.0700		35757	4.70					
95.0800		119800	15.74					
96.0800		15478	2.03					
97.0800		19617	2.58					
105.0600		94930	12.47					
106.0700		27538	3.62					
107.0800		109622	14.40					
108.0800		39812	5.23					
109.0900	1	100038	13.14					
110.1000	1	12389	1.63					
111.1000		17271	2.27					
115.0400		9074	1.19					
117.0600		22741	2.99					
119.0800		119892	15.75					
120.0800		42930	5.64					
121.0900		102730	13.50					
122.1000		123190	16.19					
123.1100	1	89326	11.74					
124.1100	1	10701	1.41					
125.1200	1	9671	1.27					
128.0500		8625	1.13					
129.0600		13788	1.81					
131.0800		36129	4.75					
132.0800		14886	1.96					
133.0900		119596	15.71					
134.1000		69674	9.15					
135.1100		131450	17.27					
136.1200		100489	13.20					
137.1300		41551	5.46					
141.0700		8163	1.07					
143.0900		14269	1.87					
145.1000		38027	5.00					
146.1000		18406	2.42					
147.1100		89957	11.82					
148.1200		59183	7.78					
149.1300		62077	8.16					
150.1300		15947	2.10					
157.1000		12340	1.62					
159.1200		30601	4.02					
160.1300		10386	1.36					
161.1300		81931	10.77					
162.1400		44107	5.80					
163.1400		30622	4.02					
171.1100		9755	1.28					
173.1300		21444	2.82					
175.1500		59153	7.77					
176.1500		18515	2.43					
177.1600		17252	2.27					
187.1500		21995	2.89					
188.1700		10092	1.33					
189.1700		181984	23.91					
190.1800		62133	8.16					
191.1700		20481	2.69					
201.1700		12906	1.70					
202.1900		7636	1.00					
203.1800	1	164231	21.58					
204.1900	1	34954	4.59					
205.2000	1	17210	2.26					
207.0800		8705	1.14					
215.1800		12019	1.58					
217.2600		10405	1.37					
218.2200	1	761052	100.00					
219.2200	1	147857	19.43					
220.2300	1	13750	1.81					
229.2000		7914	1.04					
231.2200		12033	1.58					
243.2200		8102	1.06					
249.1900		14747	1.94					
255.2100		8632	1.13					
257.2300		16933	2.22					
270.2400		16385	2.15					
271.2400		11899	1.56					
272.2500		14072	1.85					
365.3400		14723	1.93					

Analysis Report

Spectrum Peaks

m/z	Z	Abund	Abund %	m/z (Calc)	Diff (ppm)	Ion Species	Formula	Ion Type
393.3800		8075	1.06					
408.3900	1	22532	2.96					
409.4000	1	8763	1.15					
453.4000		9373	1.23					
468.4300	1	27498	3.61					
469.4400	1	9941	1.31					

Spectrum Identification Table

Best ID Source	Name	Formula	Species	m/z	Diff (ppm)	CAS	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (DB)	Score (MFG)	Lib/DB
Yes LibSearch	Noruns-12-ene	C29H48			0-00-0		82.41	82.41			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Methyl commate A	C32H52O4			0-00-0		81.12	81.12			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Olean-12-en-3-ol, acetate, (3.beta.)-	C32H52O2			1616-93-9		70.03	70.03			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	12-Oleanen-3-yl acetate, (3.alpha.)-	C32H52O2			33055-28-6		68.21	68.21			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Boron, 1,5-cyclooctanediy[(2,4-pentanediiiminato-N,N')-, (t-4)-	C13H23BN2			136704-99-9		65.14	65.14			W11N17main.L

Best Name	Formula	m/z (prec.)	CAS	RT (DB)	RT Diff	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (Fwd)	Score (Rev)	Lib/DB
Yes Noruns-12-ene	C29H48		0-00-0			82.41	82.41			W11N17main.L

Observed Spectrum

Mirror Plot

Library Spectrum

+ Scan (rt: 70.607-70.750 min) Peak 16 from + BPC Scan (Methyl commate A; C32H52O4)

Analysis Report

Spectrum Peaks

m/z	Z	Abund	Abund %	m/z (Calc)	Diff (ppm)	Ion Species	Formula	Ion Type
53.0400		15511	2.08					
55.0600		103515	13.85					
57.0700		23904	3.20					
67.0500		69423	9.29					
68.0600		32132	4.30					
69.0700	1	132410	17.71					
70.0800	1	9713	1.30					
71.0600	1	18228	2.44					
77.0400		30492	4.08					
79.0500		81624	10.92					
80.0600		19064	2.55					
81.0700		134451	17.99					
82.0700		21150	2.83					
83.0800		38691	5.18					
85.0700		10519	1.41					
91.0500		92086	12.32					
92.0600		18079	2.42					
93.0700		142917	19.12					
94.0700		50016	6.69					
95.0800		165042	22.08					
96.0800		21693	2.90					
97.0900		25045	3.35					
105.0600		121659	16.28					
106.0700		35636	4.77					
107.0800		157753	21.10					
108.0900		66805	8.94					
109.1000	1	142410	19.05					
110.1000	1	20498	2.74					
111.1000		22446	3.00					
115.0500		10748	1.44					
117.0600		26528	3.55					
119.0800		147662	19.75					
120.0900		54505	7.29					
121.1000		154110	20.62					
122.1000		135380	18.11					
123.1100	1	114578	15.33					
124.1100	1	13532	1.81					
125.1100	1	11072	1.48					
128.0500		10268	1.37					
129.0600		15844	2.12					
131.0800		43160	5.77					
132.0900		19602	2.62					
133.0900		140745	18.83					
134.1000		85149	11.39					
135.1100		169830	22.72					
136.1200		123580	16.53					
137.1300		52228	6.99					
143.0900		16155	2.16					
145.1000		48763	6.52					
146.1100		23039	3.08					
147.1200		116346	15.56					
148.1200		71202	9.53					
149.1300		79229	10.60					
150.1400		20522	2.75					
157.1000		14124	1.89					
159.1200		41254	5.52					
160.1300		15503	2.07					
161.1400		105019	14.05					
162.1400		51375	6.87					
163.1500		40743	5.45					
171.1200		11224	1.50					
173.1300		32097	4.29					
174.1400		10822	1.45					
175.1500		83779	11.21					
176.1600		25209	3.37					
177.1600		25009	3.35					
187.1500		39274	5.25					
188.1700		18531	2.48					
189.1700		255512	34.18					
190.1800		92815	12.42					
191.1800		47516	6.36					
201.1700		29051	3.89					
202.1800		18078	2.42					
203.1900		186574	24.96					
204.1900		57029	7.63					
205.2000		34241	4.58					
206.2100		11040	1.48					
215.1900		18745	2.51					
216.2000		16165	2.16					
217.2400		18898	2.53					
218.2300	1	747494	100.00					
219.2300	1	141569	18.94					
220.2300	1	13143	1.76					
229.2100		19060	2.55					
231.2200		15365	2.06					
243.2200		10272	1.37					
249.1900		23806	3.18					
255.2100		12152	1.63					
257.2400		22902	3.06					
270.2300		17954	2.40					
271.2500		15416	2.06					
272.2500		16224	2.17					
297.2700		13730	1.84					

Analysis Report

Spectrum Peaks

m/z	Z	Abund	Abund %	m/z (Calc)	Diff (ppm)	Ion Species	Formula	Ion Type
365.3400		28212	3.77					
393.3700		20841	2.79					
408.3900	1	36761	4.92					
409.4000	1	13700	1.83					
453.4100		15341	2.05					
468.4400	1	40985	5.48					
469.4400	1	14571	1.95					

Spectrum Identification Table

Best ID Source	Name	Formula	Species	m/z	Diff (ppm)	CAS	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (DB)	Score (MFG)	Lib/DB
Yes LibSearch	Methyl commate A	C32H52O4				0-00-0	81.99	81.99			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Noruns-12-ene	C29H48				0-00-0	80.26	80.26			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Methyl commate E	C31H50O5				0-00-0	72.84	72.84			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Methyl commate B	C31H50O3				0-00-0	70.63	70.63			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Olean-12-en-3-ol, acetate, (3.beta.)-	C32H52O2				1616-93-9	69.31	69.31			W11N17main.L

Best Name	Formula	m/z (prec.)	CAS	RT (DB)	RT Diff	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (Fwd)	Score (Rev)	Lib/DB
Yes Methyl commate A	C32H52O4		0-00-0			81.99	81.99			W11N17main.L

Observed Spectrum

Mirror Plot

Library Spectrum

+ Scan (rt: 70.750-70.979 min) Peak 17 from + BPC Scan (Lup-20(29)-en-3-ol, acetate, (3.beta.)-; C32H52O2)

Analysis Report

Spectrum Peaks

m/z	Z	Abund	Abund %	m/z (Calc)	Diff (ppm)	Ion Species	Formula	Ion Type
53.0500		27920	6.93					
55.0600		132417	32.85					
57.0700		28925	7.18					
67.0600		138638	34.39					
68.0600		119193	29.57					
69.0700		175901	43.64					
71.0600		30115	7.47					
77.0400		49162	12.20					
79.0500		137418	34.09					
80.0600		29553	7.33					
81.0700		222887	55.29					
82.0700		39780	9.87					
83.0800		52336	12.98					
91.0600		130483	32.37					
92.0700		27255	6.76					
93.0700		260389	64.59					
94.0700		83048	20.60					
95.0800		262544	65.13					
96.0900		37829	9.38					
97.0900		37082	9.20					
105.0700		155281	38.52					
106.0800		47197	11.71					
107.0800		269082	66.75					
108.0900		137961	34.22					
109.1000		237915	59.02					
110.1000		44023	10.92					
111.1000		33135	8.22					
117.0600		24737	6.14					
119.0800		175576	43.55					
120.0900		72522	17.99					
121.1000		275934	68.45					
122.1100		112647	27.94					
123.1100	1	157727	39.13					
124.1200	1	19941	4.95					
131.0800		41794	10.37					
132.0900		27511	6.82					
133.1000		144598	35.87					
134.1100		102999	25.55					
135.1100		238800	59.24					
136.1300		149590	37.11					
137.1400		69946	17.35					
145.1000		59153	14.67					
146.1100		26843	6.66					
147.1200		155094	38.47					
148.1300		79533	19.73					
149.1400		106415	26.40					
150.1400		30932	7.67					
159.1200		55923	13.87					
160.1300		27981	6.94					
161.1400		140990	34.98					
162.1500		53037	13.16					
163.1500		61390	15.23					
173.1400		56650	14.05					
174.1500		21049	5.22					
175.1600		130163	32.29					
176.1600		39029	9.68					
177.1600		46068	11.43					
187.1500		90725	22.51					
188.1700		44005	10.92					
189.1700		403116	100.00					
190.1800		169219	41.98					
191.1800	1	139288	34.55					
192.1900	1	24810	6.15					
201.1700		83707	20.77					
202.1800		42019	10.42					
203.1900		159166	39.48					
204.2000		123129	30.54					
205.2100		88452	21.94					
206.2200		32776	8.13					
215.1900		34917	8.66					
216.2000		54037	13.40					
217.2100		44178	10.96					
218.2200	1	176975	43.90					
219.2200	1	43398	10.77					
229.2100		60948	15.12					
230.2100		19836	4.92					
231.2200		17287	4.29					
249.1900	1	51772	12.84					
250.2000	1	14170	3.52					
255.2100		14009	3.48					
257.2400		31585	7.84					
262.2000		20190	5.01					
271.2500		15846	3.93					
272.2500		14300	3.55					
276.2200		28308	7.02					
289.2300		16260	4.03					
297.2700		47528	11.79					
298.2800		36070	8.95					
299.2900		26084	6.47					
339.3100		15188	3.77					
357.3000		33986	8.43					
358.3100		25476	6.32					
365.3400	1	60010	14.89					

Analysis Report

Spectrum Peaks

m/z	Z	Abund	Abund %	m/z (Calc)	Diff (ppm)	Ion Species	Formula	Ion Type
366.3400	1	18598	4.61					
393.3700		37463	9.29					
408.3900	1	53350	13.23					
409.4000	1	20550	5.10					
453.4100		32668	8.10					
468.4300	1	72438	17.97					
469.4400	1	25653	6.36					

Spectrum Identification Table

Best ID Source	Name	Formula	Species	m/z	Diff (ppm)	CAS	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (DB)	Score (MFG)	Lib/DB
Yes LibSearch	Lup-20(29)-en-3-ol, acetate, (3.beta.)-	C32H52O2				1617-68-1	69.35	69.35			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Methyl commate B	C31H50O3			0-00-0		68.64	68.64			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Solanesol	C45H74O			0-00-0		68.03	68.03			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Methyl commate E	C31H50O5			0-00-0		64.92	64.92			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Boron, 1,5-cyclooctanediyl(2,4-pentanediiiminato-N,N')-, (t-4)-	C13H23BN2			136704-99-9		64.00	64.00			W11N17main.L

Best Name	Formula	m/z (prec.)	CAS	RT (DB)	RT Diff	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (Fwd)	Score (Rev)	Lib/DB
Yes Lup-20(29)-en-3-ol, acetate, (3.beta.)-	C32H52O2		1617-68-1	49.783		69.35	69.35			W11N17main.L

Observed Spectrum

Mirror Plot

Library Spectrum

+ Scan (rt: 70.979-71.054 min) Peak 18 from + BPC Scan (Methyl commate B; C31H50O3)

Analysis Report

Spectrum Peaks

m/z	Z	Abund	Abund %	m/z (Calc)	Diff (ppm)	Ion Species	Formula	Ion Type
53.0500		23554	7.47					
55.0600		107371	34.04					
57.0600		23478	7.44					
65.0300		11500	3.65					
67.0600		115827	36.72					
68.0600		101563	32.20					
69.0700		138041	43.76					
71.0600		22680	7.19					
77.0400		42421	13.45					
79.0500		114942	36.44					
80.0700		23820	7.55					
81.0700		177472	56.26					
82.0700		31351	9.94					
83.0800		40597	12.87					
91.0600		110593	35.06					
92.0600		22266	7.06					
93.0700		214689	68.06					
94.0700		66206	20.99					
95.0800		210040	66.58					
96.0900		28868	9.15					
97.0900		29458	9.34					
105.0700		127747	40.50					
106.0700		38073	12.07					
107.0900		219228	69.50					
108.0900		107739	34.15					
109.1000		188318	59.70					
110.1000		33768	10.70					
111.1000		26318	8.34					
117.0600		20775	6.59					
119.0800		141391	44.82					
120.1000		57933	18.36					
121.1000		227886	72.24					
122.1000		85360	27.06					
123.1100	1	123511	39.15					
124.1200	1	14928	4.73					
131.0800		34434	10.92					
132.0900		21874	6.93					
133.1000		116190	36.83					
134.1100		82096	26.02					
135.1200		192149	60.91					
136.1200		117174	37.14					
137.1400		54570	17.30					
145.1000		49379	15.65					
146.1100		21283	6.75					
147.1200		125583	39.81					
148.1300		61427	19.47					
149.1300		85029	26.95					
150.1400		26154	8.29					
159.1200		47177	14.95					
160.1300		22699	7.20					
161.1400		115689	36.67					
162.1400		41186	13.06					
163.1500		49833	15.80					
173.1300		46897	14.87					
174.1400		17544	5.56					
175.1500		106946	33.90					
176.1600		30757	9.75					
177.1600		38000	12.05					
187.1500		74897	23.74					
188.1700		35591	11.28					
189.1700		315458	100.00					
190.1800		129559	41.07					
191.1800	1	109574	34.73					
192.1900	1	18855	5.98					
201.1700		68773	21.80					
202.1800		34685	11.00					
203.1900		123334	39.10					
204.2000		97302	30.84					
205.2100		68346	21.67					
206.2100		25056	7.94					
215.1900		29743	9.43					
216.2000		44512	14.11					
217.2000		36256	11.49					
218.2200	1	101458	32.16					
219.2200	1	26578	8.43					
229.2200	1	55735	17.67					
230.2200	1	16958	5.38					
231.2200	1	14180	4.49					
249.1900		39414	12.49					
255.2100		12546	3.98					
257.2400		25760	8.17					
262.2000		15860	5.03					
271.2500		13850	4.39					
276.2200		22617	7.17					
289.2300		12554	3.98					
297.2700		46119	14.62					
298.2800		32024	10.15					
299.2900		22357	7.09					
339.3100		15877	5.03					
357.3000		27501	8.72					
358.3000		20395	6.47					
365.3400	1	65819	20.86					
366.3400	1	19401	6.15					

Spectrum Peaks

m/z	Z	Abund	Abund %	m/z (Calc)	Diff (ppm)	Ion Species	Formula	Ion Type
393.3700	1	35345	11.20					
394.3700	1	11462	3.63					
408.3900	1	53796	17.05					
409.4000	1	19451	6.17					
453.4100		26747	8.48					
468.4400	1	60481	19.17					
469.4400	1	20210	6.41					

Spectrum Identification Table

Best ID Source	Name	Formula	Species	m/z	Diff (ppm)	CAS	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (DB)	Score (MFG)	Lib/DB
Yes LibSearch	Methyl commate B	C31H50O3			0-00-0		68.43	68.43			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Lup-20(29)-en-3-ol, acetate, (3.beta.)-	C32H52O2			1617-68-1		67.83	67.83			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Solanesol	C45H74O			0-00-0		67.31	67.31			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Boron, 1,5-cyclooctanediyl(2,4-pentanediiiminato-N,N')-, (t-4)-	C13H23BN2			136704-99-9		63.07	63.07			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Methyl commate E	C31H50O5			0-00-0		63.05	63.05			W11N17main.L

Best Name	Formula	m/z (prec.)	CAS	RT (DB)	RT Diff	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (Fwd)	Score (Rev)	Lib/DB
Yes Methyl commate B	C31H50O3		0-00-0			68.43	68.43			W11N17main.L

Observed Spectrum

Mirror Plot

Library Spectrum

+ Scan (rt: 71.672-71.803 min) Peak 19 from + BPC Scan (Iron, tricarbonyl[N-(phenyl-2-pyridinylmethylene)benzenamine-N,N']-; C21H14FeN2O3)

Analysis Report

Spectrum Peaks

m/z	Z	Abund	Abund %	m/z (Calc)	Diff (ppm)	Ion Species	Formula	Ion Type
53.0300		2999	1.78					
54.0400		4635	2.75					
55.0500		50516	29.92					
56.0600		24246	14.36					
57.0700	1	168818	100.00					
58.0700	1	8260	4.89					
67.0300		12514	7.41					
68.0500		9411	5.57					
69.0700		43787	25.94					
70.0700		22491	13.32					
71.0800	1	129899	76.95					
72.0800	1	7379	4.37					
73.0200	1	2999	1.78					
77.0200		2767	1.64					
79.0400		6587	3.90					
81.0500		14114	8.36					
82.0600		12314	7.29					
83.0800		37035	21.94					
84.0800		15163	8.98					
85.0900	1	98717	58.48					
86.0900	1	7063	4.18					
91.0400		8194	4.85					
92.0300		1850	1.10					
93.0600		7705	4.56					
94.0600		2833	1.68					
95.0700		12298	7.28					
96.0700		8946	5.30					
97.0900		34872	20.66					
98.0900		11633	6.89					
99.1000		36351	21.53					
100.0800		4682	2.77					
105.0500		7212	4.27					
106.0500		1970	1.17					
107.0700		7907	4.68					
108.0600		3740	2.22					
109.0800		8372	4.96					
110.0900		4471	2.65					
111.1000		18575	11.00					
112.1000		8782	5.20					
113.1100	1	22283	13.20					
114.1000	1	2216	1.31					
115.0300	1	1889	1.12					
117.0300		2325	1.38					
119.0600		6231	3.69					
120.0500		3753	2.22					
121.0800		7378	4.37					
122.0800		3296	1.95					
123.0900		5405	3.20					
124.0900		3068	1.82					
125.1100		9697	5.74					
126.1100		7068	4.19					
127.1300		16042	9.50					
128.0900		2926	1.73					
129.0500		2296	1.36					
131.0500		2976	1.76					
133.0800		5672	3.36					
134.0700		2989	1.77					
135.0900		6690	3.96					
136.1000		3551	2.10					
137.0900		2960	1.75					
138.1100		2359	1.40					
139.1200		4009	2.37					
140.1400		5640	3.34					
141.1400		12894	7.64					
142.1000		2671	1.58					
143.0700		2990	1.77					
145.0900		4498	2.66					
147.0900		6712	3.98					
148.1000		2446	1.45					
149.1000		3348	1.98					
154.1500		4999	2.96					
155.1600		8987	5.32					
156.1200		2201	1.30					
159.1100		3021	1.79					
161.1100		3863	2.29					
163.1100		2394	1.42					
168.1700		4126	2.44					
169.1800		6896	4.08					
175.1200		2976	1.76					
177.1100		1905	1.13					
182.2000		2782	1.65					
183.1900		5394	3.20					
189.1500		5591	3.31					
190.1600		2167	1.28					
191.1100		2812	1.67					
196.2000		2785	1.65					
197.2000		4720	2.80					
203.1600		2968	1.76					
207.0500		6675	3.95					
210.2100		2340	1.39					
211.2300		3753	2.22					
218.2100		5336	3.16					
225.2700		2624	1.55					

Analysis Report

Spectrum Peaks

m/z	Z	Abund	Abund %	m/z (Calc)	Diff (ppm)	Ion Species	Formula	Ion Type
239.2500		2904	1.72					
253.2300		2230	1.32					
267.2700		2127	1.26					
281.1700		4094	2.43					
365.3800		2822	1.67					
393.4000		2002	1.19					
396.4100		2929	1.74					

Spectrum Identification Table

Best ID Source	Name	Formula	Species	m/z	Diff (ppm)	CAS	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (DB)	Score (MFG)	Lib/DB
Yes LibSearch	Iron, tricarbonyl[N-(phenyl-2-pyridinylmethylene)benzenamine-N,N']-	C21H14FeN2O3				74764-11-7	67.79	67.79			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	1,1-Dideuterio-hexadecanyl methane sulfonate	C17H34D2O3S				56555-04-5	66.16	66.16			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	2-Azido-2,4,4,6,6,8,8-heptamethylnonane	C16H33N3				997443-71-2	64.16	64.16			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	2,2-Dideutero heptadecanal	C17H32D2O				56555-01-2	63.81	63.81			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Trihexadecyl borate	C48H99BO3				2665-11-4	63.59	63.59			W11N17main.L

Best Name	Formula	m/z (prec.)	CAS	RT (DB)	RT Diff	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (Fwd)	Score (Rev)	Lib/DB
Yes Iron, tricarbonyl[N-(phenyl-2-pyridinylmethylene)benzenamine-N,N']-	C21H14FeN2O3		74764-11-7			67.79	67.79			W11N17main.L

Observed Spectrum

Mirror Plot

Library Spectrum

+ Scan (rt: 4.283-4.363 min) Peak 1 from + TIC Scan ((2R,3R)-2-Methylbutane-1,3-diol; C5H12O2)

Analysis Report

Spectrum Peaks

m/z	Z	Abund	Abund %	m/z (Calc)	Diff (ppm)	Ion Species	Formula	Ion Type
56.0300		9298	1.08					
60.0200		11364	1.32					
61.0300	1	607061	70.45					
62.0300	1	14617	1.70					
63.0100		120936	14.04					
70.0500		37123	4.31					
72.0700		9727	1.13					
73.0700	1	861646	100.00					
74.0600	1	57780	6.71					
75.0500	1	52766	6.12					
77.0300		13441	1.56					
88.0500		15558	1.81					
91.0400		20197	2.34					

Spectrum Identification Table

Best ID Source	Name	Formula	Species	m/z	Diff (ppm)	CAS	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (DB)	Score (MFG)	Lib/DB
Yes LibSearch	(2R,3R)-2-Methylbutane-1,3-diol	C5H12O2				997014-05-6	60.09	60.09			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	(2S,3R)-2-Methylbutane-1,3-diol	C5H12O2				997014-05-5	57.63	57.63			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	3,3,5,5-Tetrauteriomethoxycyclohexane	C7H10D4O				997021-68-1	52.05	52.05			W11N17main.L

Best Name	Formula	m/z (prec.)	CAS	RT (DB)	RT Diff	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (Fwd)	Score (Rev)	Lib/DB
Yes (2R,3R)-2-Methylbutane-1,3-diol	C5H12O2		997014-05-6	14.317		60.09	60.09			W11N17main.L

Observed Spectrum

Mirror Plot

Library Spectrum

+ Scan (rt: 19.223-19.366 min) Peak 2 from + TIC Scan (Tolualdehyde [methylbenzaldehyde]; C8H8O)

Analysis Report

Spectrum Peaks

m/z	Z	Abund	Abund %	m/z (Calc)	Diff (ppm)	Ion Species	Formula	Ion Type
51.0300		24782	5.18					
52.0300		7427	1.55					
53.0200		13801	2.89					
55.0200		10890	2.28					
59.0300		7701	1.61					
60.0200		11627	2.43					
60.9900		8473	1.77					
62.0100		18573	3.89					
63.0200		38328	8.02					
64.0300		11330	2.37					
65.0300		70354	14.72					
66.0300		16117	3.37					
74.0100		8409	1.76					
75.0200		8284	1.73					
77.0200		11266	2.36					
78.0300		5985	1.25					
89.0300		21941	4.59					
90.0300		6769	1.42					
91.0500		220385	46.11					
92.0500		24251	5.07					
94.0300		38352	8.02					
103.0400		6128	1.28					
105.0200		9380	1.96					
118.0300		7646	1.60					
119.0400		122383	25.61					
120.0500	1	477958	100.00					
121.0500	1	42391	8.87					

Spectrum Identification Table

Best ID Source	Name	Formula	Species	m/z	Diff (ppm)	CAS	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (DB)	Score (MFG)	Lib/DB
Yes LibSearch	Tolualdehyde [methylbenzaldehyde]	C8H8O				0-00-0	82.08	82.08			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	1,3,2-Benzodioxaborole	C6H5BO2				274-07-7	75.67	75.67			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Benethamine	C31H35N3O4S				997970-03-8	74.94	74.94			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	4,5-cyclopenteno-1,2-diazine	C7H8N2				6250-96-0	74.25	74.25			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Catecholborane	C6H5BO2				274-07-7	73.67	73.67			W11N17main.L

Best Name	Formula	m/z (prec.)	CAS	RT (DB)	RT Diff	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (Fwd)	Score (Rev)	Lib/DB
Yes Tolualdehyde [methylbenzaldehyde]	C8H8O		0-00-0			82.08	82.08			W11N17main.L

Observed Spectrum

Mirror Plot

Library Spectrum

+ Scan (rt: 41.488-41.974 min)

Peak 3 from + TIC Scan (p-Coumaric acid; C9H8O3)

Analysis Report

Spectrum Peaks

m/z	Z	Abund	Abund %	m/z (Calc)	Diff (ppm)	Ion Species	Formula	Ion Type
51.0200		6417	5.70					
53.0100		5417	4.81					
55.0100		3554	3.16					
59.0200		1257	1.12					
59.1100		1981	1.76					
60.9900		2078	1.85					
62.0000		5922	5.26					
63.0100		13557	12.04					
64.0100		4593	4.08					
65.0200		20526	18.23					
66.0100		2832	2.51					
67.0100		1333	1.18					
68.0000		2493	2.21					
69.0000		3328	2.95					
73.9100		1701	1.51					
74.9700		1182	1.05					
75.0100		1948	1.73					
77.0200		8057	7.15					
78.0200		1733	1.54					
79.0200		4454	3.96					
81.0300		1139	1.01					
82.0200		1289	1.14					
89.0300		13526	12.01					
90.0200		4376	3.89					
91.0400	1	29560	26.25					
92.0000		2063	1.83					
92.0500	1	1642	1.46					
94.0300		2573	2.28					
95.0000		1330	1.18					
101.0200		1616	1.44					
107.0300	1	14958	13.28					
108.0200	1	1879	1.67					
117.0200		1536	1.36					
118.0200		27143	24.10					
119.0300		28908	25.67					
120.0300		7759	6.89					
121.0300		2675	2.38					
123.0000		1761	1.56					
134.9900		1344	1.19					
135.0400		1794	1.59					
136.0300		3816	3.39					
146.0200		4395	3.90					
147.0300	1	49325	43.80					
148.0400	1	5023	4.46					
163.0400		41906	37.21					
164.0400	1	112620	100.00					
165.0400	1	11350	10.08					
166.0400	1	1316	1.17					

Spectrum Identification Table

Best ID Source	Name	Formula	Species	m/z	Diff (ppm)	CAS	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (DB)	Score (MFG)	Lib/DB
Yes LibSearch	p-Coumaric acid	C9H8O3				7400-08-0	76.46	76.46			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	p-Coumaric acid	C9H8O3				7400-08-0	74.55	74.55			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	p-Coumaric acid, trans	C9H8O3				501-98-4	73.29	73.29			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	2-Propenoic acid, 3-(4-hydroxyphenyl)-	C9H8O3				7400-08-0	72.89	72.89			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	p-Coumaric acid	C9H8O3				7400-08-0	72.48	72.48			W11N17main.L

Best Name	Formula	m/z (prec.)	CAS	RT (DB)	RT Diff	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (Fwd)	Score (Rev)	Lib/DB
Yes p-Coumaric acid	C9H8O3		7400-08-0	26.283		76.46	76.46			W11N17main.L

Observed Spectrum

Mirror Plot

Library Spectrum

+ Scan (rt: 44.549-44.658 min) Peak 4 from + TIC Scan (Benzoic acid, 2-hydroxy-, phenylmethyl ester; C14H12O3)

Spectrum Peaks

m/z	Z	Abund	Abund %	m/z (Calc)	Diff (ppm)	Ion Species	Formula	Ion Type
51.0200		21900	1.78					
53.0200		12463	1.01					
63.0200		36326	2.95					
64.0200		19813	1.61					
65.0300		144019	11.68					
77.0300		24085	1.95					
79.0400		12881	1.04					
89.0400		26646	2.16					
90.0500		12863	1.04					
91.0500	1	1232749	100.00					
92.0500	1	125079	10.15					
93.0200	1	23232	1.88					
120.0100		16858	1.37					
121.0100		38686	3.14					
228.0900	1	149934	12.16					
229.1000	1	23159	1.88					

Spectrum Identification Table

Best ID Source	Name	Formula	Species	m/z	Diff (ppm)	CAS	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (DB)	Score (MFG)	Lib/DB
Yes	LibSearch	Benzoic acid, 2-hydroxy-, phenylmethyl ester	C14H12O3			118-58-1	72.23	72.23			W11N17main.L
No	LibSearch	Benzoic acid, 2-hydroxy-, phenylmethyl ester	C14H12O3			118-58-1	70.68	70.68			W11N17main.L
No	LibSearch	Benzoic acid, 2-hydroxy-, phenylmethyl ester	C14H12O3			118-58-1	70.48	70.48			W11N17main.L
No	LibSearch	Benzoic acid, 2-hydroxy-, phenylmethyl ester	C14H12O3			118-58-1	69.71	69.71			W11N17main.L
No	LibSearch	4-Benzyloxybenzoic acid	C14H12O3			1486-51-7	68.34	68.34			W11N17main.L
Best Name	Formula	m/z (prec.)	CAS	RT (DB)	RT Diff	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (Fwd)	Score (Rev)	Lib/DB	
Yes	Benzoic acid, 2-hydroxy-, phenylmethyl ester	C14H12O3	118-58-1	32.567		72.23	72.23			W11N17main.L	

Observed Spectrum

Mirror Plot

Library Spectrum

+ Scan (rt: 57.973-58.133 min)

Peak 5 from + TIC Scan (.alpha.-Pyrone, 4-methoxy-6-[2-(1-acetyl-p-pyridium chloride)-(E)-ethenyl]-; C15H14ClNO4)

Analysis Report

Spectrum Peaks

m/z	Z	Abund	Abund %	m/z (Calc)	Diff (ppm)	Ion Species	Formula	Ion Type
51.0300		38592	33.75					
52.0300		19435	17.00					
53.0300		50874	44.50					
54.0300		8532	7.46					
55.0200		19310	16.89					
59.0100		24618	21.53					
63.0200		21437	18.75					
64.0200		11722	10.25					
65.0300		34913	30.54					
66.0300		12536	10.96					
67.0300		14183	12.41					
68.0200		9689	8.47					
69.0200		20838	18.23					
71.0100		12845	11.23					
75.0200		7848	6.86					
77.0300		61802	54.05					
78.0400		27836	24.35					
79.0300		29567	25.86					
80.0200		10570	9.25					
81.0300		19472	17.03					
85.0200		9732	8.51					
89.0300		16795	14.69					
91.0500		45856	40.11					
92.0400		11610	10.15					
93.0200		10946	9.57					
94.0300		11998	10.49					
95.0200		14120	12.35					
97.0200		20999	18.37					
101.0100		8247	7.21					
102.0300		13817	12.08					
103.0400		25569	22.36					
104.0500		10100	8.83					
105.0400		43113	37.71					
106.0400		11659	10.20					
107.0100		19649	17.19					
108.0200		10595	9.27					
109.0200		9123	7.98					
115.0500		75403	65.95					
116.0500		19486	17.04					
117.0500		30525	26.70					
118.0500		10078	8.81					
119.0300		10408	9.10					
121.0200		18896	16.53					
122.0300		10603	9.27					
123.0300		18550	16.22					
127.0400		36275	31.73					
128.0500		70593	61.74					
129.0500		56292	49.23					
130.0600		11836	10.35					
131.0400		41561	36.35					
132.0400		22080	19.31					
133.0300		30505	26.68					
134.0300		11511	10.07					
135.0300		10162	8.89					
136.0400		44873	39.25					
139.0300	1	96848	84.71					
140.0400	1	10420	9.11					
145.0500		54944	48.06					
146.0500		14250	12.46					
147.0500		13549	11.85					
149.0200		11101	9.71					
150.0300		16103	14.08					
151.0300		9042	7.91					
155.0400		10366	9.07					
156.0600		11644	10.18					
157.0600		31446	27.50					
158.0600		12214	10.68					
159.0500		14630	12.80					
160.0500		114333	100.00					
161.0500		50260	43.96					
162.0500		13001	11.37					
165.0500		62216	54.42					
173.0500		47956	41.94					
174.0600		23742	20.77					
175.0600		9143	8.00					
184.0500		16207	14.18					
185.0600		26566	23.24					
186.0600		10075	8.81					
187.0500		10975	9.60					
188.0500		13396	11.72					
189.0500		18355	16.05					
193.0600	1	86428	75.59					
194.0600	1	10573	9.25					
201.0600		110911	97.01					
202.0600	1	48701	42.60					
203.0700	1	12071	10.56					
212.0500		19535	17.09					
213.0600		18693	16.35					
215.0600		14333	12.54					
229.0600		100566	87.96					
230.0700	1	98356	86.03					
231.0700	1	18003	15.75					
240.0400		14674	12.83					

Analysis Report

Spectrum Peaks

m/z	Z	Abund	Abund %	m/z (Calc)	Diff (ppm)	Ion Species	Formula	Ion Type
244.0800		12136	10.61					
258.0600		45297	39.62					
259.0700		29413	25.73					
261.0900		34082	29.81					
262.0900		14312	12.52					
272.0700		19516	17.07					
290.0900		36982	32.35					

Spectrum Identification Table

Best ID Source	Name	Formula	Species	m/z	Diff (ppm)	CAS	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (DB)	Score (MFG)	Lib/DB
Yes LibSearch	.alpha.-Pyrone, 4-methoxy-6-[2-(1-acetyl-p-pyridium chloride)-(E)-ethenyl]-	C15H14ClNO4				997583-25-8	50.68	50.68			W11N17main.L

Best Name	Formula	m/z (prec.)	CAS	RT (DB)	RT Diff	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (Fwd)	Score (Rev)	Lib/DB
Yes .alpha.-Pyrone, 4-methoxy-6-[2-(1-acetyl-p-pyridium chloride)-(E)-ethenyl]-	C15H14ClNO4		997583-25-8			50.68	50.68			W11N17main.L

Observed Spectrum

Mirror Plot

Library Spectrum

+ Scan (rt: 58.791-58.929 min) Peak 6 from + TIC Scan

Analysis Report

Spectrum Peaks

m/z	Z	Abund	Abund %	m/z (Calc)	Diff (ppm)	Ion Species	Formula	Ion Type
51.0300		22201	34.60					
52.0300		11951	18.63					
53.0300		32735	51.02					
54.0200		5563	8.67					
55.0300		13287	20.71					
59.0100		14222	22.17					
63.0200		12244	19.08					
64.0200		5419	8.45					
65.0300		20782	32.39					
66.0200		7449	11.61					
67.0300		9708	15.13					
68.0200		6420	10.01					
69.0200		15266	23.79					
71.0100		8098	12.62					
77.0300		35476	55.29					
78.0300		15950	24.86					
79.0300		18372	28.63					
80.0200		6752	10.52					
81.0300		13492	21.03					
83.0300		5582	8.70					
85.0200		5325	8.30					
89.0200		9245	14.41					
91.0500		26435	41.20					
92.0300		6245	9.73					
93.0300		6932	10.80					
94.0300		7606	11.86					
95.0300		9963	15.53					
97.0200		14691	22.90					
102.0200		6800	10.60					
103.0400		14375	22.41					
104.0400		5853	9.12					
105.0300		26526	41.34					
106.0300		7941	12.38					
107.0200		13119	20.45					
108.0200		6697	10.44					
109.0300		6161	9.60					
115.0400		37453	58.38					
116.0400		9167	14.29					
117.0500		16324	25.44					
118.0300		5703	8.89					
119.0300		7067	11.01					
120.0300		5645	8.80					
121.0200		12922	20.14					
122.0300		6045	9.42					
123.0300		11402	17.77					
127.0400		15376	23.97					
128.0500		27988	43.62					
129.0500		22495	35.06					
130.0400		5534	8.62					
131.0400		23911	37.27					
132.0400		12752	19.88					
133.0300		19612	30.57					
134.0200		7363	11.48					
135.0400		6520	10.16					
136.0400		19885	30.99					
139.0300	1	64159	100.00					
140.0300	1	6339	9.88					
145.0500		30340	47.29					
146.0600		8285	12.91					
147.0500		9528	14.85					
149.0200		7877	12.28					
150.0200		9486	14.79					
151.0300		6768	10.55					
156.0400		4737	7.38					
157.0600		15083	23.51					
158.0500		6175	9.62					
159.0500		8287	12.92					
160.0500		53053	82.69					
161.0500		26867	41.88					
162.0300		6981	10.88					
164.0300		5242	8.17					
165.0500		39532	61.62					
173.0500		28189	43.94					
174.0600		13377	20.85					
175.0600		5361	8.36					
184.0400		8197	12.78					
185.0500		14056	21.91					
186.0600		5990	9.34					
187.0500		6375	9.94					
188.0500		7128	11.11					
189.0600		9874	15.39					
193.0500	1	52236	81.42					
194.0500	1	6387	9.95					
201.0600		50058	78.02					
202.0600	1	24742	38.56					
203.0600	1	6578	10.25					
212.0500		10907	17.00					
213.0600		11122	17.34					
215.0600		7685	11.98					
229.0600		54083	84.30					
230.0700	1	57355	89.40					
231.0800	1	10647	16.59					
240.0400		8619	13.43					

Analysis Report

Spectrum Peaks

m/z	Z	Abund	Abund %	m/z (Calc)	Diff (ppm)	Ion Species	Formula	Ion Type
244.0800		7157	11.16					
258.0600		29421	45.86					
259.0600		17132	26.70					
261.0800		20431	31.84					
262.0900		7244	11.29					
272.0700		11552	18.01					
290.0900		20417	31.82					

+ Scan (rt: 64.405-64.725 min) Peak 7 from + TIC Scan (Solanesol; C45H74O)

Analysis Report

Spectrum Peaks

m/z	Z	Abund	Abund %	m/z (Calc)	Diff (ppm)	Ion Species	Formula	Ion Type
53.0200		2631	11.37					
54.0200		1494	6.46					
55.0500		23143	100.00					
56.0500		3169	13.69					
57.0600		9052	39.11					
60.0100		1180	5.10					
65.0000		1815	7.84					
67.0400		10113	43.70					
68.0300		3200	13.83					
69.0600		19579	84.60					
70.0500		2855	12.33					
71.0700		5867	25.35					
73.0100		2818	12.18					
77.0200		3918	16.93					
79.0400		9174	39.64					
80.0200		2066	8.93					
81.0500		14378	62.13					
82.0600		5038	21.77					
83.0600		9716	41.98					
84.0400		2030	8.77					
85.0600		3606	15.58					
91.0400		13397	57.89					
92.0200		2004	8.66					
93.0500		9903	42.79					
94.0400		3111	13.44					
95.0700		14165	61.20					
96.0500		3382	14.62					
97.0700		7201	31.11					
99.0600		2829	12.23					
105.0500		10581	45.72					
106.0400		2572	11.11					
107.0600		9567	41.34					
108.0400		4985	21.54					
109.0800		10539	45.54					
110.0600		2307	9.97					
111.0700		3394	14.67					
115.0200		2011	8.69					
117.0400		3650	15.77					
118.0300		1779	7.69					
119.0600		7791	33.66					
120.0600		4822	20.84					
121.0800		7368	31.84					
122.0600		2429	10.49					
123.0900		5309	22.94					
125.0800		1619	7.00					
128.0200		1346	5.82					
129.0400		2942	12.71					
131.0500		4908	21.21					
133.0700		6435	27.80					
134.0700		2774	11.99					
135.0800		5761	24.89					
136.0700		2228	9.63					
137.0700		3516	15.19					
138.1100		2245	9.70					
141.0400		1318	5.70					
143.0600		3489	15.08					
144.0800		1175	5.08					
145.0800		6654	28.75					
146.0500		1306	5.64					
147.0900		5575	24.09					
148.0800		1853	8.01					
149.1000		3377	14.59					
157.0900		1898	8.20					
158.1200		1552	6.71					
159.1000		4929	21.30					
160.0900		2044	8.83					
161.0900		1927	8.33					
161.1200		2669	11.53					
163.1200		1549	6.69					
171.1200		1176	5.08					
173.1100		2930	12.66					
175.1200		3305	14.28					
176.1200		1346	5.82					
177.1100		1323	5.72					
185.1100		2113	9.13					
187.1200		2529	10.93					
189.1500		4835	20.89					
191.1300		2176	9.40					
199.1100		1376	5.95					
203.1600		3296	14.24					
204.1500		1288	5.57					
205.1700		2492	10.77					
207.0900		3457	14.94					
211.1600		2324	10.04					
213.1600		4026	17.40					
215.1500		1442	6.23					
218.2100		2655	11.47					
228.1800		1445	6.24					
229.1700		6118	26.43					
231.1500		1425	6.16					
253.1700		1570	6.79					
271.1900		2026	8.75					
281.2200	1	7914	34.20					

Analysis Report

Spectrum Peaks

m/z	Z	Abund	Abund %	m/z (Calc)	Diff (ppm)	Ion Species	Formula	Ion Type
282.2100	1	1933	8.35					
296.2300		2089	9.03					
296.2800		3280	14.17					
299.2400		3511	15.17					
314.2700	1	16027	69.25					
315.2400		2443	10.55					
315.2900	1	1577	6.82					

Spectrum Identification Table

Best ID Source	Name	Formula	Species	m/z	Diff (ppm)	CAS	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (DB)	Score (MFG)	Lib/DB
Yes LibSearch	Solanesol	C45H74O				0-00-0	63.18	63.18			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Geranyl linalool isomer	C20H34O				0-00-0	60.69	60.69			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	22,23-Methylene-cholesterol;3rd diastereomer	C28H46O				0-00-0	59.96	59.96			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Geranyl linalool isomer B	C20H34O				0-00-0	59.17	59.17			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	22,23-Methylene-cholesterol;4th diastereomer	C28H46O				0-00-0	56.38	56.38			W11N17main.L

Best Name	Formula	m/z (prec.)	CAS	RT (DB)	RT Diff	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (Fwd)	Score (Rev)	Lib/DB
Yes Solanesol	C45H74O		0-00-0			63.18	63.18			W11N17main.L

Observed Spectrum

Mirror Plot

Library Spectrum

+ Scan (rt: 64.725-65.023 min) Peak 8 from + TIC Scan (Noruns-12-ene; C29H48)

Analysis Report

Spectrum Peaks

m/z	Z	Abund	Abund %	m/z (Calc)	Diff (ppm)	Ion Species	Formula	Ion Type
53.0300		3821	3.35					
54.0300		1744	1.53					
55.0500		28374	24.90					
56.0500		4607	4.04					
57.0600		21502	18.87					
59.9900		1725	1.51					
65.0100		2320	2.04					
67.0400		13963	12.25					
68.0400		4098	3.60					
69.0600		30616	26.87					
70.0600		4341	3.81					
71.0600		13348	11.71					
73.0200		3290	2.89					
77.0200		5737	5.03					
78.0100		1615	1.42					
79.0400		14520	12.74					
80.0400		4308	3.78					
81.0500		23809	20.89					
82.0600		6302	5.53					
83.0600		11436	10.04					
84.0600		2661	2.33					
85.0800		8238	7.23					
91.0400		16261	14.27					
92.0400		3343	2.93					
93.0600		17997	15.79					
94.0600		11425	10.03					
95.0700		26830	23.55					
96.0600		5334	4.68					
97.0700		8803	7.73					
98.0600		2324	2.04					
99.0800		3109	2.73					
105.0500	1	18282	16.04					
106.0300	1	1653	1.45					
106.0700	1	2503	2.20					
107.0600	1	18393	16.14					
108.0600		6739	5.91					
109.0800		17771	15.60					
110.0700		3168	2.78					
111.0800		6328	5.55					
115.0200		2742	2.41					
117.0400		4973	4.36					
118.0300		1738	1.52					
119.0600		17631	15.47					
120.0600		7349	6.45					
121.0800		16400	14.39					
122.0800		7075	6.21					
123.1000		10718	9.41					
124.0900		1874	1.64					
125.0800		2457	2.16					
128.0400		2388	2.10					
129.0500		4124	3.62					
131.0600		6683	5.86					
132.0500		2142	1.88					
133.0700		12700	11.15					
134.0800		6998	6.14					
135.0900		15531	13.63					
136.1000		9515	8.35					
137.1100		9738	8.55					
138.1100		4320	3.79					
139.0900		2364	2.07					
143.0600		3050	2.68					
145.0800		6890	6.05					
146.0800		2126	1.87					
147.1000		11990	10.52					
148.1000		5339	4.69					
149.1100		7193	6.31					
150.1000		2366	2.08					
151.1000		1702	1.49					
157.0800		2794	2.45					
159.1000		5282	4.64					
160.0900		1891	1.66					
161.1100		8462	7.43					
162.1300		3114	2.73					
163.1300		4807	4.22					
171.1000		1981	1.74					
173.1000		3512	3.08					
175.1400		11328	9.94					
176.1200		3296	2.89					
177.1300		3298	2.89					
185.0900		1701	1.49					
187.1400		3118	2.74					
189.1500		18352	16.11					
190.1600		8168	7.17					
191.1500		4646	4.08					
203.1800	1	54599	47.92					
204.1800	1	10713	9.40					
205.1900	1	5175	4.54					
207.1500		10121	8.88					
208.1400		2782	2.44					
213.1500		1688	1.48					
218.2100	1	113947	100.00					
219.2100	1	21480	18.85					
220.2000	1	2289	2.01					

Analysis Report

Spectrum Peaks

m/z	Z	Abund	Abund %	m/z (Calc)	Diff (ppm)	Ion Species	Formula	Ion Type
229.1700		2786	2.44					
257.2100		3164	2.78					
281.1700		2420	2.12					
296.2600		1841	1.62					
314.2700		2246	1.97					
411.3700		2079	1.82					
426.4200		3420	3.00					

Spectrum Identification Table

Best ID Source	Name	Formula	Species	m/z	Diff (ppm)	CAS	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (DB)	Score (MFG)	Lib/DB
Yes LibSearch	Noruns-12-ene	C29H48				0-00-0	78.95	78.95			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Methyl commate A	C32H52O4				0-00-0	71.78	71.78			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	.beta.-Amyrin	C30H50O				559-70-6	66.83	66.83			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Solanesol	C45H74O				0-00-0	64.37	64.37			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	.alpha.-Amyrin	C30H50O				638-95-9	63.99	63.99			W11N17main.L

Best Name	Formula	m/z (prec.)	CAS	RT (DB)	RT Diff	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (Fwd)	Score (Rev)	Lib/DB
Yes Noruns-12-ene	C29H48		0-00-0			78.95	78.95			W11N17main.L

Observed Spectrum

Mirror Plot

Library Spectrum

+ Scan (rt: 65.234-65.572 min) Peak 9 from + TIC Scan (Solanesol; C45H74O)

Analysis Report

Spectrum Peaks

m/z	Z	Abund	Abund %	m/z (Calc)	Diff (ppm)	Ion Species	Formula	Ion Type
53.0200		2750	9.90					
54.0300		1547	5.57					
55.0500		19130	68.89					
56.0500		3266	11.76					
57.0600		10724	38.62					
59.9900		1818	6.55					
67.0400		10061	36.23					
68.0400		3641	13.11					
69.0600		27770	100.00					
70.0600		3400	12.24					
71.0600		7303	26.30					
73.0200		3822	13.76					
77.0100		3788	13.64					
78.0100		1240	4.46					
79.0400		8510	30.65					
80.0300		2619	9.43					
81.0500		14290	51.46					
82.0500		5065	18.24					
83.0700		9277	33.41					
84.0500		2142	7.71					
85.0700		4468	16.09					
91.0400		10417	37.51					
92.0200		1523	5.48					
93.0500		10673	38.43					
94.0500		3112	11.21					
95.0700		15157	54.58					
96.0600		6115	22.02					
97.0700		7087	25.52					
98.0400		1825	6.57					
99.0500		1699	6.12					
105.0500		10649	38.35					
106.0500		2505	9.02					
107.0600		10377	37.37					
108.0600		2925	10.53					
109.0800		12856	46.29					
110.0700		2554	9.20					
111.0800		4204	15.14					
115.0200		2117	7.63					
117.0400		3618	13.03					
118.0300		1535	5.53					
119.0600		9365	33.72					
120.0500		4346	15.65					
121.0700		8840	31.83					
122.0800		3384	12.19					
123.0900		6680	24.05					
124.0800		1695	6.10					
125.0800		2346	8.45					
127.0500		1241	4.47					
128.0300		1725	6.21					
129.0500		3374	12.15					
131.0500		5121	18.44					
132.0500		1575	5.67					
133.0700		7412	26.69					
134.0700		3169	11.41					
135.0800		7944	28.61					
136.0800		2911	10.48					
137.0900		3738	13.46					
139.0600		1327	4.78					
141.0500		1197	4.31					
143.0400		1327	4.78					
143.0900		1252	4.51					
145.0800		5384	19.39					
147.0900		6616	23.82					
148.0900		2041	7.35					
149.1000		4751	17.11					
157.0800		2402	8.65					
159.1000		4673	16.83					
160.1000		1370	4.93					
161.1100		4695	16.91					
163.0900		2048	7.38					
171.1000		1857	6.69					
173.1200		5121	18.44					
175.1200		3956	14.24					
177.1200		1872	6.74					
185.1000		1876	6.75					
187.1300		3519	12.67					
189.1400		4358	15.69					
190.1300		1373	4.94					
191.1100		2418	8.71					
199.1200		1420	5.11					
201.1100		1720	6.19					
201.1600		1360	4.90					
203.1500		3453	12.43					
205.1600		1822	6.56					
207.0600		5220	18.80					
213.1500		1688	6.08					
215.1600		1988	7.16					
218.1900		3378	12.16					
229.1800		1967	7.08					
241.1900		1212	4.37					
255.1600		1475	5.31					
257.2100		1312	4.72					
271.2200		1690	6.09					

Analysis Report

Spectrum Peaks

m/z	Z	Abund	Abund %	m/z (Calc)	Diff (ppm)	Ion Species	Formula	Ion Type
281.1000		2382	8.58					
313.2300		1276	4.59					
393.3700	1	6015	21.66					
394.3400	1	1264	4.55					
411.3900	1	10731	38.64					
412.3700	1	2830	10.19					
426.4400		1391	5.01					

Spectrum Identification Table

Best ID Source	Name	Formula	Species	m/z	Diff (ppm)	CAS	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (DB)	Score (MFG)	Lib/DB
Yes LibSearch	Solanesol	C45H74O			0-00-0		67.49	67.49			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Geranyl linalool isomer	C20H34O			0-00-0		64.03	64.03			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Geranyl linalool isomer B	C20H34O			0-00-0		61.64	61.64			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	19-di-torulosol	C20H33DO2			1438-63-7		57.64	57.64			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Linoleic acid (2E,6E,10E)-3,7,11,15-tetramethyl-2,6,10,14-hexadecatetraen-1-yl ester	C38H64O2			524958-65-4		57.24	57.24			W11N17main.L

Best Name	Formula	m/z (prec.)	CAS	RT (DB)	RT Diff	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (Fwd)	Score (Rev)	Lib/DB
Yes Solanesol	C45H74O		0-00-0			67.49	67.49			W11N17main.L

Observed Spectrum

Mirror Plot

Library Spectrum

+ Scan (rt: 66.362-66.739 min) Peak 10 from + TIC Scan (Noruns-12-ene; C29H48)

Analysis Report

Spectrum Peaks

m/z	Z	Abund	Abund %	m/z (Calc)	Diff (ppm)	Ion Species	Formula	Ion Type
53.0400		19805	7.40					
55.0600		115964	43.33					
56.0600		12021	4.49					
57.0600		42177	15.76					
67.0500		85819	32.06					
68.0600		44359	16.57					
69.0700	1	166866	62.34					
70.0700	1	14284	5.34					
71.0600		31713	11.85					
77.0300		31262	11.68					
79.0500		82361	30.77					
80.0600		18686	6.98					
81.0600		128693	48.08					
82.0700		28622	10.69					
83.0800		42374	15.83					
85.0700		11990	4.48					
91.0500		87081	32.53					
92.0600		18352	6.86					
93.0600		129415	48.35					
94.0700		41479	15.50					
95.0800		159655	59.65					
96.0800		25655	9.58					
97.0800		28707	10.73					
105.0600		98184	36.68					
106.0700		28947	10.81					
107.0800		135522	50.63					
108.0800		57615	21.53					
109.0900		130316	48.69					
110.1000		22380	8.36					
111.0900		23178	8.66					
117.0600		24095	9.00					
119.0800		109201	40.80					
120.0800		42573	15.91					
121.0900		126857	47.40					
122.1000		77199	28.84					
123.1100	1	87655	32.75					
124.1100	1	12150	4.54					
129.0600		13969	5.22					
131.0800		34625	12.94					
132.0800		15302	5.72					
133.0900		92969	34.73					
134.1000		61188	22.86					
135.1100		129499	48.38					
136.1200		67065	25.06					
137.1300		38979	14.56					
143.0800		13004	4.86					
145.1000		40381	15.09					
146.1000		15358	5.74					
147.1100		88976	33.24					
148.1200		52454	19.60					
149.1300		67770	25.32					
150.1300		17398	6.50					
157.1000		11911	4.45					
159.1200		37455	13.99					
160.1200		15933	5.95					
161.1300		74684	27.90					
162.1400		32312	12.07					
163.1500		39428	14.73					
173.1300		40574	15.16					
174.1400		12311	4.60					
175.1500		67779	25.32					
176.1500		19238	7.19					
177.1600		25131	9.39					
187.1500		36595	13.67					
188.1600		13924	5.20					
189.1700		122097	45.62					
190.1700		48300	18.05					
191.1800		39452	14.74					
201.1700		28197	10.53					
202.1800		14695	5.49					
203.1800		94271	35.22					
204.1900		36974	13.81					
205.2000		30282	11.31					
206.2100		13653	5.10					
207.1800		82016	30.64					
208.1800		22675	8.47					
215.1900		15203	5.68					
216.2000		10675	3.99					
217.2100		18642	6.96					
218.2200	1	267659	100.00					
219.2200	1	58985	22.04					
220.2100	1	14194	5.30					
229.2100		18551	6.93					
231.2200		14216	5.31					
257.2300		17061	6.37					
271.2500		18613	6.95					
272.2500		10648	3.98					
286.2800		21788	8.14					
297.2700		11800	4.41					
315.2800		12736	4.76					
339.3100		12361	4.62					
365.3400		25028	9.35					
393.3700	1	35373	13.22					

Analysis Report

Spectrum Peaks

m/z	Z	Abund	Abund %	m/z (Calc)	Diff (ppm)	Ion Species	Formula	Ion Type
394.3800	1	10861	4.06					
408.3900		17672	6.60					
408.4100		11106	4.15					
409.4000		10182	3.80					
411.3900		28872	10.79					
426.4200	1	43977	16.43					
427.4200	1	14452	5.40					

Spectrum Identification Table

Best ID Source	Name	Formula	Species	m/z	Diff (ppm)	CAS	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (DB)	Score (MFG)	Lib/DB
Yes LibSearch	Noruns-12-ene	C29H48				0-00-0	73.49	73.49			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Methyl commate E	C31H50O5				0-00-0	71.53	71.53			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Methyl commate A	C32H52O4				0-00-0	71.13	71.13			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Methyl commate B	C31H50O3				0-00-0	70.19	70.19			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Solanesol	C45H74O				0-00-0	69.74	69.74			W11N17main.L

Best Name	Formula	m/z (prec.)	CAS	RT (DB)	RT Diff	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (Fwd)	Score (Rev)	Lib/DB
Yes Noruns-12-ene	C29H48		0-00-0			73.49	73.49			W11N17main.L

Observed Spectrum

Mirror Plot

Library Spectrum

+ Scan (rt: 66.968-67.140 min) Peak 11 from + TIC Scan (Solanesol; C45H74O)

Analysis Report

Spectrum Peaks

m/z	Z	Abund	Abund %	m/z (Calc)	Diff (ppm)	Ion Species	Formula	Ion Type
53.0300		4980	10.10					
54.0300		3184	6.46					
55.0500		27104	54.98					
56.0500		4481	9.09					
57.0600		14442	29.30					
59.9900		2014	4.09					
65.0200		2957	6.00					
67.0400		18943	38.43					
68.0600		9126	18.51					
69.0600		49297	100.00					
70.0700		5511	11.18					
71.0600		12032	24.41					
73.0200		4519	9.17					
77.0200		6793	13.78					
78.0300		2014	4.09					
79.0400		14818	30.06					
80.0500		8536	17.32					
81.0600		27427	55.64					
82.0600		8010	16.25					
83.0700		11647	23.63					
84.0500		3437	6.97					
85.0700		6630	13.45					
91.0500		16926	34.34					
92.0500		5913	11.99					
93.0600		25668	52.07					
94.0600		6567	13.32					
95.0700		21780	44.18					
96.0700		7462	15.14					
97.0700		10060	20.41					
98.0600		3151	6.39					
99.0700		11202	22.72					
100.0400		9055	18.37					
105.0500		12609	25.58					
106.0400		3275	6.64					
107.0700		16862	34.21					
108.0600		7318	14.85					
109.0800		16569	33.61					
110.0700		3827	7.76					
111.0800		5744	11.65					
113.0600		2590	5.25					
117.0400		3653	7.41					
119.0700		14741	29.90					
120.0600		6452	13.09					
121.0800		14231	28.87					
122.0900		6450	13.08					
123.1000		12692	25.75					
124.0900		3021	6.13					
125.0900		3367	6.83					
127.0700		1899	3.85					
128.0300		1925	3.90					
129.0500		3279	6.65					
131.0700		4528	9.19					
133.0800		10462	21.22					
134.0800		5657	11.48					
135.0900		13374	27.13					
136.1100		9402	19.07					
137.1100		6268	12.71					
138.1000		2882	5.85					
139.0800		1882	3.82					
141.0800		5370	10.89					
143.0700		2387	4.84					
145.0800		4908	9.96					
147.1000		8417	17.07					
148.1000		4014	8.14					
149.1100		6475	13.14					
150.1000		1849	3.75					
151.1000		2138	4.34					
156.1000		4697	9.53					
157.0900		3351	6.80					
159.1100		4280	8.68					
161.1200		8842	17.94					
162.1100		2492	5.05					
163.1100		3633	7.37					
169.1000		2273	4.61					
171.1000		2029	4.12					
173.1100		4061	8.24					
175.1300		4740	9.62					
177.1200		2234	4.53					
187.1200		3569	7.24					
189.1500		8268	16.77					
190.1500		2300	4.67					
191.1100		3145	6.38					
201.1500		2299	4.66					
203.1600		3776	7.66					
204.1700		3027	6.14					
205.1800		3112	6.31					
207.0700		8084	16.40					
218.2000		4353	8.83					
229.1900		2094	4.25					
241.1700		2194	4.45					
253.0500		1765	3.58					
259.2000		2411	4.89					
281.0900		3645	7.39					

Analysis Report

Spectrum Peaks

m/z	Z	Abund	Abund %	m/z (Calc)	Diff (ppm)	Ion Species	Formula	Ion Type
365.3400		1844	3.74					
393.3600	1	5353	10.86					
394.3600	1	1877	3.81					
408.3600		1975	4.01					
411.3900	1	7732	15.68					
412.4000	1	2313	4.69					
426.4000		2631	5.34					

Spectrum Identification Table

Best ID Source	Name	Formula	Species	m/z	Diff (ppm)	CAS	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (DB)	Score (MFG)	Lib/DB
Yes LibSearch	Solanesol	C45H74O				0-00-0	70.75	70.75			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Geranyl linalool isomer	C20H34O				0-00-0	69.39	69.39			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Geranyl linalool isomer B	C20H34O				0-00-0	67.65	67.65			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	.beta.-D-Mannofuranoside, 2,3:5,6-di-ethylboranediyl-cis-nerolidyl	C25H42B2O6				997916-21-0	63.09	63.09			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Pogostol	C16H28O				21698-41-9	62.24	62.24			W11N17main.L

Best Name	Formula	m/z (prec.)	CAS	RT (DB)	RT Diff	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (Fwd)	Score (Rev)	Lib/DB
Yes Solanesol	C45H74O		0-00-0			70.75	70.75			W11N17main.L

Observed Spectrum

Mirror Plot

Library Spectrum

+ Scan (rt: 67.437-67.758 min) Peak 12 from + TIC Scan (3-(2,2-Dimethyl-6-methylenecyclohexyl)-1-propanol; C12H20D2O)

Analysis Report

Spectrum Peaks

m/z	Z	Abund	Abund %	m/z (Calc)	Diff (ppm)	Ion Species	Formula	Ion Type
53.0300		3906	8.47					
54.0300		2758	5.98					
55.0500		27528	59.71					
56.0500		5833	12.65					
57.0600		29289	63.54					
58.0400		4261	9.24					
59.0400		2106	4.57					
60.0000		2255	4.89					
65.0200		2020	4.38					
67.0400		14777	32.06					
68.0500		7791	16.90					
69.0600		46099	100.00					
70.0600		6429	13.95					
71.0700	1	28160	61.09					
72.0600	1	2207	4.79					
73.0200		5029	10.91					
77.0100		4440	9.63					
78.0100		1601	3.47					
79.0400		10471	22.71					
80.0400		6331	13.73					
81.0600		26400	57.27					
82.0600		7508	16.29					
83.0700		14110	30.61					
84.0400		6038	13.10					
85.0600		14359	31.15					
91.0400		9015	19.56					
92.0400		2853	6.19					
93.0600		13891	30.13					
94.0600		6171	13.39					
95.0700		18815	40.81					
96.0700		6397	13.88					
97.0600		14683	31.85					
98.0600		6592	14.30					
99.0700		41417	89.84					
100.0400	1	44886	97.37					
101.0400	1	4656	10.10					
105.0500		6739	14.62					
106.0300		1849	4.01					
107.0600		9238	20.04					
108.0700		4762	10.33					
109.0800		12117	26.28					
110.0700		3373	7.32					
111.0800		7140	15.49					
112.0500		2275	4.93					
113.0500		8442	18.31					
114.0400		4388	9.52					
115.0400		2583	5.60					
117.0300		2177	4.72					
119.0600		7376	16.00					
120.0400		3813	8.27					
121.0700		9378	20.34					
122.0700		3801	8.25					
123.0900		9488	20.58					
124.0800		3709	8.05					
125.0800		4183	9.07					
126.0700		1542	3.35					
127.0900		7343	15.93					
128.0600		2330	5.06					
129.0500		2671	5.79					
131.0500		2428	5.27					
133.0700		5540	12.02					
134.0800		2980	6.46					
135.0800		7950	17.25					
136.1000		6187	13.42					
137.1100		6392	13.87					
138.0900		8158	17.70					
139.0900		2562	5.56					
141.0900		18181	39.44					
142.0800		3764	8.16					
143.0700		1899	4.12					
145.0700		2492	5.41					
147.0800		4879	10.58					
148.1000		1828	3.97					
149.1000		4699	10.19					
151.1000		2228	4.83					
155.1100		1517	3.29					
156.1100		24511	53.17					
157.1100		9451	20.50					
159.0900		2143	4.65					
161.1200		3598	7.81					
163.1000		2381	5.17					
169.1100		8074	17.51					
173.1000		1604	3.48					
175.1200		2469	5.36					
184.1300		2534	5.50					
185.1300		1973	4.28					
187.1200		1396	3.03					
189.1500		3461	7.51					
191.0900		2341	5.08					
197.1300		1527	3.31					
203.1600		2111	4.58					
207.0600		7627	16.54					
209.0600		1445	3.13					

Analysis Report

Spectrum Peaks

m/z	Z	Abund	Abund %	m/z (Calc)	Diff (ppm)	Ion Species	Formula	Ion Type
218.1900		2541	5.51					
253.0600		1835	3.98					
281.0800		3374	7.32					
332.3300		2313	5.02					
390.3900		2075	4.50					
393.3900		3237	7.02					
446.4400		1440	3.12					

Spectrum Identification Table

Best ID Source	Name	Formula	Species	m/z	Diff (ppm)	CAS	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (DB)	Score (MFG)	Lib/DB
Yes LibSearch	3-(2,2-Dimethyl-6-methylenecyclohexyl)-1-propanol	C12H20D2O				3419-32-7	62.55	62.55			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Nerolidol-epoxyacetate	C17H28O4				0-00-0	61.57	61.57			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	.beta.-D-Mannofuranoside, 2,3,5,6-diethylboranediyl-cis-nerolidyl	C25H42B2O6				997916-21-0	61.57	61.57			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	2-propenyl 3-cyclohexylpropanoate	C12H20O2				0-00-0	59.40	59.40			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Geranyl linalool isomer B	C20H34O				0-00-0	58.51	58.51			W11N17main.L

Best Name	Formula	m/z (prec.)	CAS	RT (DB)	RT Diff	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (Fwd)	Score (Rev)	Lib/DB
Yes 3-(2,2-Dimethyl-6-methylenecyclohexyl)-1-propanol	C12H20D2O		3419-32-7			62.55	62.55			W11N17main.L

Observed Spectrum

Mirror Plot

Library Spectrum

+ Scan (rt: 68.416-68.513 min) Peak 13 from + TIC Scan (Iron, tricarbonyl[N-(phenyl-2-pyridinylmethylene)benzenamine-N,N']-; C21H14FeN2O3)

Analysis Report

Spectrum Peaks

m/z	Z	Abund	Abund %	m/z (Calc)	Diff (ppm)	Ion Species	Formula	Ion Type
53.0300		3656	1.90					
54.0500		6251	3.24					
55.0600		62664	32.50					
56.0600		29749	15.43					
57.0700	1	192826	100.00					
58.0700	1	9127	4.73					
67.0400		15644	8.11					
68.0500		13296	6.90					
69.0700		55864	28.97					
70.0700		27316	14.17					
71.0800	1	144358	74.86					
72.0800	1	8236	4.27					
73.0300	1	4499	2.33					
77.0100		3039	1.58					
79.0400		6599	3.42					
80.0300		2995	1.55					
81.0500		16228	8.42					
82.0600		18813	9.76					
83.0800		47427	24.60					
84.0800		18728	9.71					
85.0900	1	109063	56.56					
86.0900	1	7347	3.81					
91.0400		7078	3.67					
93.0500		7395	3.83					
94.0500		3112	1.61					
95.0700		14349	7.44					
96.0700		12679	6.58					
97.0800		43379	22.50					
98.0900		14132	7.33					
99.1000	1	38499	19.97					
100.0800	1	4067	2.11					
105.0500		5385	2.79					
107.0600		5954	3.09					
108.0600		3029	1.57					
109.0800		10259	5.32					
110.0800		6218	3.22					
111.1000		23314	12.09					
112.1000		10525	5.46					
113.1100		23762	12.32					
119.0500		5276	2.74					
120.0200		2377	1.23					
121.0800		5901	3.06					
122.0600		2299	1.19					
123.1000		5920	3.07					
124.0900		4027	2.09					
125.1100		11437	5.93					
126.1100		7935	4.12					
127.1300	1	16809	8.72					
128.0800	1	2079	1.08					
129.0500	1	2024	1.05					
131.0400		2107	1.09					
133.0600		4349	2.26					
134.0600		2045	1.06					
135.0800		5243	2.72					
136.0800		2720	1.41					
137.1000		3190	1.65					
138.1200		3604	1.87					
139.1200		4750	2.46					
140.1400		6451	3.35					
141.1400		12294	6.38					
145.0700		2243	1.16					
147.0700		3942	2.04					
149.1000		2589	1.34					
153.1200		2703	1.40					
154.1600		5389	2.79					
155.1600		9216	4.78					
161.1000		2927	1.52					
168.1500		4341	2.25					
169.1800		7168	3.72					
175.1200		2331	1.21					
182.1900		3648	1.89					
183.2000		5199	2.70					
189.1500		5841	3.03					
191.1000		2699	1.40					
196.2100		3048	1.58					
197.1900		4736	2.46					
203.1600		2865	1.49					
204.1700		2955	1.53					
205.1900		4737	2.46					
207.0600	1	7509	3.89					
208.0800	1	1941	1.01					
210.2100		2709	1.40					
211.2300		3815	1.98					
218.1900		2900	1.50					
224.2400		2059	1.07					
225.2600		3206	1.66					
239.2700		2210	1.15					
253.1600		2632	1.37					
267.2500		2708	1.40					
281.1100		2686	1.39					
281.2200		2150	1.12					
408.4500		2976	1.54					

Analysis Report

Spectrum Identification Table

Best ID Source	Name	Formula	Species	m/z	Diff (ppm)	CAS	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (DB)	Score (MFG)	Lib/DB
Yes LibSearch	Iron, tricarbonyl[[N-(phenyl-2-pyridinylmethylene)benzenamine-N,N']-	C21H14FeN2O3				74764-11-7	69.86	69.86			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Trihexadecyl borate	C48H98B03				2665-11-4	68.99	68.99			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	1,1-Dideuterio-hexadecanyl methane sulfonate	C17H34D2O3S				56555-04-5	68.36	68.36			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	2-Azido-2,4,4,6,6,8,8-heptamethylnonane	C16H33N3				997443-71-2	66.27	66.27			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	2-Octadecyloxy-1,1,2,2-tetra deuterioethanol	C20H38D4O2				56599-39-4	65.74	65.74			W11N17main.L

Best Name	Formula	m/z (prec.)	CAS	RT (DB)	RT Diff	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (Fwd)	Score (Rev)	Lib/DB
Yes Iron, tricarbonyl[[N-(phenyl-2-pyridinylmethylene)benzenamine-N,N']-	C21H14FeN2O3		74764-11-7			69.86	69.86			W11N17main.L

Observed Spectrum

Mirror Plot

Library Spectrum

+ Scan (rt: 68.633-68.965 min) Peak 14 from + TIC Scan (Noruns-12-ene; C29H48)

Analysis Report

Spectrum Peaks

m/z	Z	Abund	Abund %	m/z (Calc)	Diff (ppm)	Ion Species	Formula	Ion Type
53.0300		5771	2.09					
55.0600		43658	15.78					
56.0500		5184	1.87					
57.0700		16813	6.08					
58.0400		3202	1.16					
59.0300		3515	1.27					
65.0200		3325	1.20					
67.0400		22883	8.27					
68.0500		6483	2.34					
69.0700		59886	21.65					
70.0600		5662	2.05					
71.0600		12190	4.41					
73.0200		3719	1.34					
77.0300		10153	3.67					
79.0500		28002	10.12					
80.0500		8011	2.90					
81.0600		43917	15.87					
82.0600		8295	3.00					
83.0700		17203	6.22					
84.0600		3329	1.20					
85.0700		6937	2.51					
91.0500		29787	10.77					
92.0500		6313	2.28					
93.0600		40055	14.48					
94.0700		24056	8.70					
95.0700		53149	19.21					
96.0700		9296	3.36					
97.0800		13397	4.84					
105.0500		37469	13.54					
106.0600		8556	3.09					
107.0700		40833	14.76					
108.0800		13379	4.84					
109.0800	1	38154	13.79					
110.0900	1	5360	1.94					
111.0900	1	10949	3.96					
115.0400		4151	1.50					
117.0500		9088	3.28					
119.0700		39245	14.19					
120.0700		13526	4.89					
121.0800		38255	13.83					
122.0900		15101	5.46					
123.1000		21571	7.80					
124.0900		4447	1.61					
125.1000		3850	1.39					
128.0400		3593	1.30					
129.0500		6017	2.18					
131.0700		12881	4.66					
132.0700		4571	1.65					
133.0800		29464	10.65					
134.0900		17470	6.31					
135.1000		36303	13.12					
136.1100		21475	7.76					
137.1200	1	21430	7.75					
138.1200	1	3706	1.34					
143.0700		5261	1.90					
145.0900		13147	4.75					
146.1100		3405	1.23					
147.1100		27870	10.07					
148.1100		12188	4.41					
149.1200		15985	5.78					
150.1200		4769	1.72					
157.0800		4534	1.64					
159.1200		11065	4.00					
160.1100		3793	1.37					
161.1200		21090	7.62					
162.1300		10453	3.78					
163.1300		10566	3.82					
171.1000		3408	1.23					
173.1200		8727	3.15					
175.1400		29089	10.51					
176.1400		8110	2.93					
177.1500		8117	2.93					
187.1400		8178	2.96					
188.1500		3282	1.19					
189.1600		51427	18.59					
190.1700		19520	7.06					
191.1700		10531	3.81					
201.1600		6577	2.38					
202.1700		4399	1.59					
203.1800	1	133957	48.42					
204.1900	1	27994	10.12					
205.2000	1	14134	5.11					
206.2100		4114	1.49					
207.0600		7876	2.85					
215.1900		3431	1.24					
217.2300		3480	1.26					
218.2200	1	276646	100.00					
219.2200	1	51974	18.79					
220.2100	1	4963	1.79					
229.2100		3928	1.42					
231.2100		3980	1.44					
255.2100		3457	1.25					
257.2300		7364	2.66					

Analysis Report

Spectrum Peaks

m/z	Z	Abund	Abund %	m/z (Calc)	Diff (ppm)	Ion Species	Formula	Ion Type
270.2400		3213	1.16					
271.2400		4476	1.62					
281.0800		3432	1.24					
365.3500		4952	1.79					
393.3700		5323	1.92					
408.3900		7157	2.59					
468.4300		5732	2.07					

Spectrum Identification Table

Best ID Source	Name	Formula	Species	m/z	Diff (ppm)	CAS	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (DB)	Score (MFG)	Lib/DB
Yes LibSearch	Noruns-12-ene	C29H48				0-00-0	81.50	81.50			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Methyl commate A	C32H52O4				0-00-0	79.07	79.07			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Olean-12-en-3-ol, acetate, (3.beta.)-	C32H52O2				1616-93-9	70.88	70.88			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	.beta.-Amyrin	C30H50O				559-70-6	65.71	65.71			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	12-Oleanen-3-yl acetate, (3.alpha.)-	C32H52O2				33055-28-6	65.46	65.46			W11N17main.L

Best Name	Formula	m/z (prec.)	CAS	RT (DB)	RT Diff	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (Fwd)	Score (Rev)	Lib/DB
Yes Noruns-12-ene	C29H48		0-00-0			81.50	81.50			W11N17main.L

Observed Spectrum

Mirror Plot

Library Spectrum

+ Scan (rt: 70.321-70.607 min) Peak 15 from + TIC Scan (Noruns-12-ene; C29H48)

Analysis Report

Spectrum Peaks

m/z	Z	Abund	Abund %	m/z (Calc)	Diff (ppm)	Ion Species	Formula	Ion Type
53.0400		10776	1.42					
55.0600		84016	11.04					
56.0600		8011	1.05					
57.0600		21065	2.77					
67.0500		44509	5.85					
68.0600		9136	1.20					
69.0700	1	107933	14.18					
70.0700	1	8450	1.11					
71.0600	1	14261	1.87					
77.0300		21681	2.85					
79.0500		56962	7.48					
80.0600		13969	1.84					
81.0600		96134	12.63					
82.0700		14170	1.86					
83.0800		30804	4.05					
85.0700		9700	1.27					
91.0500		68761	9.03					
92.0500		13495	1.77					
93.0600		95250	12.52					
94.0700		35757	4.70					
95.0800		119800	15.74					
96.0800		15478	2.03					
97.0800		19617	2.58					
105.0600		94930	12.47					
106.0700		27538	3.62					
107.0800		109622	14.40					
108.0800		39812	5.23					
109.0900	1	100038	13.14					
110.1000	1	12389	1.63					
111.1000		17271	2.27					
115.0400		9074	1.19					
117.0600		22741	2.99					
119.0800		119892	15.75					
120.0800		42930	5.64					
121.0900		102730	13.50					
122.1000		123190	16.19					
123.1100	1	89326	11.74					
124.1100	1	10701	1.41					
125.1200	1	9671	1.27					
128.0500		8625	1.13					
129.0600		13788	1.81					
131.0800		36129	4.75					
132.0800		14886	1.96					
133.0900		119596	15.71					
134.1000		69674	9.15					
135.1100		131450	17.27					
136.1200		100489	13.20					
137.1300		41551	5.46					
141.0700		8163	1.07					
143.0900		14269	1.87					
145.1000		38027	5.00					
146.1000		18406	2.42					
147.1100		89957	11.82					
148.1200		59183	7.78					
149.1300		62077	8.16					
150.1300		15947	2.10					
157.1000		12340	1.62					
159.1200		30601	4.02					
160.1300		10386	1.36					
161.1300		81931	10.77					
162.1400		44107	5.80					
163.1400		30622	4.02					
171.1100		9755	1.28					
173.1300		21444	2.82					
175.1500		59153	7.77					
176.1500		18515	2.43					
177.1600		17252	2.27					
187.1500		21995	2.89					
188.1700		10092	1.33					
189.1700		181984	23.91					
190.1800		62133	8.16					
191.1700		20481	2.69					
201.1700		12906	1.70					
202.1900		7636	1.00					
203.1800	1	164231	21.58					
204.1900	1	34954	4.59					
205.2000	1	17210	2.26					
207.0800		8705	1.14					
215.1800		12019	1.58					
217.2600		10405	1.37					
218.2200	1	761052	100.00					
219.2200	1	147857	19.43					
220.2300	1	13750	1.81					
229.2000		7914	1.04					
231.2200		12033	1.58					
243.2200		8102	1.06					
249.1900		14747	1.94					
255.2100		8632	1.13					
257.2300		16933	2.22					
270.2400		16385	2.15					
271.2400		11899	1.56					
272.2500		14072	1.85					
365.3400		14723	1.93					

Analysis Report

Spectrum Peaks

m/z	Z	Abund	Abund %	m/z (Calc)	Diff (ppm)	Ion Species	Formula	Ion Type
393.3800		8075	1.06					
408.3900	1	22532	2.96					
409.4000	1	8763	1.15					
453.4000		9373	1.23					
468.4300	1	27498	3.61					
469.4400	1	9941	1.31					

Spectrum Identification Table

Best ID Source	Name	Formula	Species	m/z	Diff (ppm)	CAS	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (DB)	Score (MFG)	Lib/DB
Yes LibSearch	Noruns-12-ene	C29H48			0-00-0		82.41	82.41			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Methyl commate A	C32H52O4			0-00-0		81.12	81.12			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Olean-12-en-3-ol, acetate, (3.beta.)-	C32H52O2			1616-93-9		70.03	70.03			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	12-Oleanen-3-yl acetate, (3.alpha.)-	C32H52O2			33055-28-6		68.21	68.21			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Boron, 1,5-cyclooctanediy[(2,4-pentanediiiminato-N,N')-, (t-4)-	C13H23BN2			136704-99-9		65.14	65.14			W11N17main.L

Best Name	Formula	m/z (prec.)	CAS	RT (DB)	RT Diff	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (Fwd)	Score (Rev)	Lib/DB
Yes Noruns-12-ene	C29H48		0-00-0			82.41	82.41			W11N17main.L

Observed Spectrum

Mirror Plot

Library Spectrum

+ Scan (rt: 70.607-70.710 min) Peak 16 from + TIC Scan (Methyl commate A; C32H52O4)

Analysis Report

Spectrum Peaks

m/z	Z	Abund	Abund %	m/z (Calc)	Diff (ppm)	Ion Species	Formula	Ion Type
53.0400		15147	1.67					
55.0600		107711	11.86					
57.0700		24876	2.74					
67.0500		65507	7.22					
68.0600		23515	2.59					
69.0700	1	137134	15.11					
70.0800	1	10007	1.10					
71.0600	1	17771	1.96					
77.0400		30374	3.35					
79.0500		80976	8.92					
80.0500		19098	2.10					
81.0700		133301	14.68					
82.0700		20245	2.23					
83.0800		39591	4.36					
85.0700		11121	1.22					
91.0500		95011	10.47					
92.0600		18411	2.03					
93.0700		139616	15.38					
94.0700		49792	5.48					
95.0800		166122	18.30					
96.0800		20973	2.31					
97.0900		25294	2.79					
105.0700		128275	14.13					
106.0700		37118	4.09					
107.0800		157115	17.31					
108.0900		62144	6.85					
109.1000	1	141684	15.61					
110.1000	1	18840	2.08					
111.1000		22913	2.52					
115.0500		11710	1.29					
117.0600		29223	3.22					
119.0800		158118	17.42					
120.0900		56996	6.28					
121.1000		151734	16.71					
122.1000		152080	16.75					
123.1100	1	119828	13.20					
124.1100	1	13918	1.53					
125.1200	1	11989	1.32					
128.0500		11336	1.25					
129.0600		17697	1.95					
131.0800		47580	5.24					
132.0900		20385	2.25					
133.0900		154041	16.97					
134.1000		91499	10.08					
135.1100		177276	19.53					
136.1200		132589	14.61					
137.1300		54843	6.04					
141.0700		10853	1.20					
143.0900		18168	2.00					
145.1000		51985	5.73					
146.1100		24606	2.71					
147.1200		122396	13.48					
148.1200		77438	8.53					
149.1300		83590	9.21					
150.1400		21205	2.34					
157.1000		15834	1.74					
159.1300		42887	4.72					
160.1400		15265	1.68					
161.1400		111284	12.26					
162.1400		56315	6.20					
163.1500		42153	4.64					
171.1200		12485	1.38					
173.1300		31779	3.50					
174.1400		10405	1.15					
175.1500		85773	9.45					
176.1600		25920	2.86					
177.1600		24997	2.75					
187.1500		36440	4.01					
188.1600		17020	1.87					
189.1700		262659	28.93					
190.1800		91530	10.08					
191.1800		40041	4.41					
201.1700		25048	2.76					
202.1800		16960	1.87					
203.1900	1	211275	23.27					
204.1900	1	54296	5.98					
205.2100	1	30622	3.37					
215.1900		18631	2.05					
216.2000		12807	1.41					
217.2500		17693	1.95					
218.2300	1	907816	100.00					
219.2300	1	170911	18.83					
220.2200	1	15579	1.72					
229.2100		15736	1.73					
231.2200		16679	1.84					
243.2200		10940	1.21					
249.1900		23024	2.54					
255.2100		12600	1.39					
257.2400		24273	2.67					
270.2300		21295	2.35					
271.2500		16926	1.86					
272.2500		18345	2.02					
297.2800		11104	1.22					

Analysis Report

Spectrum Peaks

m/z	Z	Abund	Abund %	m/z (Calc)	Diff (ppm)	Ion Species	Formula	Ion Type
365.3400		27504	3.03					
393.3700		20849	2.30					
408.3900	1	38204	4.21					
409.4000	1	14231	1.57					
453.4100		15206	1.68					
468.4400	1	42292	4.66					
469.4500	1	14968	1.65					

Spectrum Identification Table

Best ID Source	Name	Formula	Species	m/z	Diff (ppm)	CAS	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (DB)	Score (MFG)	Lib/DB
Yes LibSearch	Methyl commate A	C32H52O4				0-00-0	81.72	81.72			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Noruns-12-ene	C29H48				0-00-0	80.86	80.86			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Methyl commate E	C31H50O5				0-00-0	72.09	72.09			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Olean-12-en-3-ol, acetate, (3.beta.)-	C32H52O2				1616-93-9	69.48	69.48			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	12-Oleanen-3-yl acetate, (3.alpha.)-	C32H52O2				33055-28-6	68.22	68.22			W11N17main.L

Best Name	Formula	m/z (prec.)	CAS	RT (DB)	RT Diff	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (Fwd)	Score (Rev)	Lib/DB
Yes Methyl commate A	C32H52O4		0-00-0			81.72	81.72			W11N17main.L

Observed Spectrum

Mirror Plot

Library Spectrum

+ Scan (rt: 70.710-71.059 min) Peak 17 from + TIC Scan (Methyl commate B; C31H50O3)

Analysis Report

Spectrum Peaks

m/z	Z	Abund	Abund %	m/z (Calc)	Diff (ppm)	Ion Species	Formula	Ion Type
53.0500		25139	7.05					
55.0600		120079	33.68					
57.0700		26408	7.41					
67.0600		124234	34.85					
68.0600		105511	29.59					
69.0700		158023	44.32					
71.0600		26730	7.50					
77.0400		44676	12.53					
79.0500		123798	34.72					
80.0600		26525	7.44					
81.0700		198941	55.80					
82.0700		35301	9.90					
83.0800		47016	13.19					
91.0600		118524	33.24					
92.0600		24453	6.86					
93.0700		232931	65.33					
94.0700		74019	20.76					
95.0800		234612	65.80					
96.0900		33538	9.41					
97.0900		33286	9.34					
105.0700		140595	39.43					
106.0700		42573	11.94					
107.0800		240586	67.48					
108.0900		121769	34.15					
109.1000		211735	59.39					
110.1000		38687	10.85					
111.1000		29657	8.32					
117.0600		22866	6.41					
119.0800		158496	44.46					
120.0900		65137	18.27					
121.1000		246922	69.26					
122.1100		102194	28.66					
123.1100	1	140593	39.43					
124.1200	1	17629	4.94					
131.0800		38327	10.75					
132.0900		24645	6.91					
133.1000		131304	36.83					
134.1100		92516	25.95					
135.1100		213774	59.96					
136.1300		133993	37.58					
137.1400		62387	17.50					
145.1000		53792	15.09					
146.1100		24229	6.80					
147.1200		139418	39.10					
148.1300		71213	19.97					
149.1300		95275	26.72					
150.1400		27913	7.83					
159.1200		50783	14.24					
160.1300		24919	6.99					
161.1400		126794	35.56					
162.1400		47754	13.39					
163.1500		54859	15.39					
173.1400		50698	14.22					
174.1400		18800	5.27					
175.1500		116632	32.71					
176.1600		34671	9.72					
177.1600		40998	11.50					
187.1500		80423	22.56					
188.1700		38802	10.88					
189.1700		356531	100.00					
190.1800		148588	41.68					
191.1800	1	121468	34.07					
192.1900	1	21549	6.04					
201.1700		73595	20.64					
202.1800		37148	10.42					
203.1900		143931	40.37					
204.2000		108188	30.34					
205.2100		76910	21.57					
206.2200		28459	7.98					
207.1400		12330	3.46					
215.1900		31314	8.78					
216.2000		47444	13.31					
217.2100		38981	10.93					
218.2200	1	175610	49.26					
219.2200	1	41550	11.65					
229.2100		54815	15.37					
230.2100		17629	4.94					
231.2200		15671	4.40					
249.1900		44938	12.60					
255.2100		13093	3.67					
257.2400		28255	7.92					
262.2000		17452	4.89					
271.2500		14632	4.10					
272.2500		12843	3.60					
276.2200		24507	6.87					
289.2300		13984	3.92					
297.2700		43273	12.14					
298.2800		32000	8.98					
299.2900		23008	6.45					
339.3100		14370	4.03					
357.3000		29439	8.26					
358.3000		22029	6.18					
365.3400	1	56951	15.97					

Spectrum Peaks

m/z	Z	Abund	Abund %	m/z (Calc)	Diff (ppm)	Ion Species	Formula	Ion Type
366.3400	1	17422	4.89					
393.3700		34420	9.65					
408.3900	1	50307	14.11					
409.4000	1	19059	5.35					
453.4100		28671	8.04					
468.4300	1	64179	18.00					
469.4400	1	22522	6.32					

Spectrum Identification Table

Best ID Source	Name	Formula	Species	m/z	Diff (ppm)	CAS	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (DB)	Score (MFG)	Lib/DB
Yes LibSearch	Methyl commate B	C31H50O3			0-00-0		68.94	68.94			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Lup-20(29)-en-3-ol, acetate, (3.beta.)-	C32H52O2			1617-68-1		68.90	68.90			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Solanesol	C45H74O			0-00-0		67.98	67.98			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Methyl commate E	C31H50O5			0-00-0		65.26	65.26			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Boron, 1,5-cyclooctanediy[(2,4-pentanediiiminato-N,N')-, (t-4)-	C13H23BN2			136704-99-9		64.17	64.17			W11N17main.L

Best Name	Formula	m/z (prec.)	CAS	RT (DB)	RT Diff	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (Fwd)	Score (Rev)	Lib/DB
Yes Methyl commate B	C31H50O3		0-00-0			68.94	68.94			W11N17main.L

Observed Spectrum

Mirror Plot

Library Spectrum

+ Scan (rt: 71.672-71.826 min) Peak 18 from + TIC Scan (Iron, tricarbonyl[N-(phenyl-2-pyridinylmethylene)benzenamine-N,N']-; C21H14FeN2O3)

Analysis Report

Spectrum Peaks

m/z	Z	Abund	Abund %	m/z (Calc)	Diff (ppm)	Ion Species	Formula	Ion Type
53.0300		2838	1.90					
54.0300		4266	2.85					
55.0500		46294	30.97					
56.0600		21758	14.56					
57.0700	1	149473	100.00					
58.0600	1	7351	4.92					
67.0300		12093	8.09					
68.0500		8931	5.98					
69.0700		40323	26.98					
70.0700		20188	13.51					
71.0800	1	114819	76.82					
72.0800	1	6550	4.38					
73.0200	1	2994	2.00					
77.0200		2818	1.89					
79.0400		6538	4.37					
81.0500		13872	9.28					
82.0600		11796	7.89					
83.0700		34089	22.81					
84.0800		13660	9.14					
85.0900	1	87071	58.25					
86.0900	1	6234	4.17					
91.0400		8156	5.46					
93.0600		7666	5.13					
94.0600		2803	1.88					
95.0700		12119	8.11					
96.0700		8537	5.71					
97.0900		32111	21.48					
98.0900		10514	7.03					
99.1000		32091	21.47					
100.0700		4240	2.84					
105.0500		7354	4.92					
106.0500		1988	1.33					
107.0700		7880	5.27					
108.0600		3645	2.44					
109.0800		8324	5.57					
110.0900		4270	2.86					
111.1000		17189	11.50					
112.1000		7899	5.28					
113.1100	1	19660	13.15					
114.1000	1	1977	1.32					
115.0300	1	1874	1.25					
117.0400		2381	1.59					
119.0600		6178	4.13					
120.0600		3783	2.53					
121.0800		7346	4.91					
122.0700		3274	2.19					
123.0900		5348	3.58					
124.0900		2926	1.96					
125.1100		8947	5.99					
126.1100		6324	4.23					
127.1300		14169	9.48					
128.0900		2743	1.84					
129.0500		2297	1.54					
131.0500		3008	2.01					
133.0700		5640	3.77					
134.0700		2964	1.98					
135.0900		6650	4.45					
136.1000		3485	2.33					
137.1000		2918	1.95					
138.1100		2225	1.49					
139.1200		3735	2.50					
140.1400		5035	3.37					
141.1400		11486	7.68					
142.1000		2401	1.61					
143.0700		2941	1.97					
145.0900		4594	3.07					
147.0900		6839	4.58					
148.1000		2417	1.62					
149.1000		3282	2.20					
154.1500		4464	2.99					
155.1600		7774	5.20					
156.1200		1886	1.26					
159.1100		3024	2.02					
161.1200		3859	2.58					
163.1100		2389	1.60					
168.1700		3666	2.45					
169.1800		6146	4.11					
175.1200		2939	1.97					
177.1100		1873	1.25					
182.2000		2489	1.66					
183.1900		4725	3.16					
187.1200		1830	1.22					
189.1500		5515	3.69					
190.1600		2139	1.43					
191.1100		2750	1.84					
196.1900		2482	1.66					
197.2000		4174	2.79					
203.1600		3023	2.02					
207.0400		6682	4.47					
210.2100		2006	1.34					
211.2300		3287	2.20					
218.2100		5337	3.57					
225.2700		2276	1.52					

Analysis Report

Spectrum Peaks

m/z	Z	Abund	Abund %	m/z (Calc)	Diff (ppm)	Ion Species	Formula	Ion Type
239.2500		2549	1.71					
253.2300		1912	1.28					
267.2700		1848	1.24					
281.1700		3777	2.53					
365.3800		2566	1.72					
393.4000		1893	1.27					
396.4000		3181	2.13					

Spectrum Identification Table

Best ID Source	Name	Formula	Species	m/z	Diff (ppm)	CAS	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (DB)	Score (MFG)	Lib/DB
Yes LibSearch	Iron, tricarbonyl[N-(phenyl-2-pyridinylmethylene)benzenamine-N,N']-	C21H14FeN2O3				74764-11-7	66.51	66.51			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	1,1-Dideuterio-hexadecanyl methane sulfonate	C17H34D2O3S				56555-04-5	65.55	65.55			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	2,2-Dideutero heptadecanal	C17H32D2O				56555-01-2	63.34	63.34			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	2-Azido-2,4,4,6,6,8,8-heptamethylnonane	C16H33N3				997443-71-2	63.33	63.33			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Trihexadecyl borate	C48H99BO3				2665-11-4	62.86	62.86			W11N17main.L

Best Name	Formula	m/z (prec.)	CAS	RT (DB)	RT Diff	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (Fwd)	Score (Rev)	Lib/DB
Yes Iron, tricarbonyl[N-(phenyl-2-pyridinylmethylene)benzenamine-N,N']-	C21H14FeN2O3		74764-11-7			66.51	66.51			W11N17main.L

Observed Spectrum

Mirror Plot

Library Spectrum

+ Scan (rt: 74.172-74.544 min) Peak 19 from + TIC Scan (Solanesol; C45H74O)

Analysis Report

Spectrum Peaks

m/z	Z	Abund	Abund %	m/z (Calc)	Diff (ppm)	Ion Species	Formula	Ion Type
53.0300		2218	11.54					
54.0200		1616	8.41					
55.0500		16379	85.23					
56.0500		3940	20.50					
57.0600		12902	67.14					
58.0300		1006	5.23					
59.9900		1483	7.72					
61.0100		4213	21.92					
65.0100		1582	8.23					
67.0400		9401	48.92					
68.0500		5358	27.88					
69.0600		17216	89.58					
70.0500		4026	20.95					
71.0700		8768	45.63					
73.0100		3290	17.12					
77.0200		3433	17.86					
79.0400		7259	37.77					
80.0400		2292	11.93					
81.0500		13108	68.21					
82.0600		7401	38.51					
83.0700		11328	58.94					
84.0600		2884	15.01					
85.0800		5214	27.13					
91.0400		8391	43.66					
92.0100		1354	7.04					
93.0500		10022	52.15					
94.0500		4136	21.52					
95.0700		15570	81.02					
96.0600		5539	28.82					
97.0800		10859	56.51					
98.0700		2636	13.72					
99.0700		2537	13.20					
103.0200		1047	5.45					
105.0500		7566	39.37					
106.0500		1965	10.23					
107.0700		11181	58.18					
108.0600		5378	27.98					
109.0800		11854	61.68					
110.0700		3083	16.04					
111.0900		6118	31.84					
112.0700		1371	7.13					
115.0300		1341	6.98					
117.0400		2087	10.86					
119.0600		8088	42.09					
120.0600		4850	25.24					
121.0800		13110	68.22					
122.0800		6349	33.04					
123.0900		8522	44.35					
124.0800		3264	16.99					
125.0900		3409	17.74					
127.0900		973	5.06					
129.0400		1366	7.11					
131.0400		3415	17.77					
132.0400		1298	6.76					
133.0700		7828	40.73					
134.0800		4492	23.37					
135.0900		9699	50.47					
136.1000		6068	31.58					
137.0900		5680	29.56					
138.0900		1564	8.14					
139.1300		995	5.18					
143.0700		1024	5.33					
145.0800		2802	14.58					
146.0500		1003	5.22					
147.0900		5696	29.64					
148.1200		1475	7.68					
149.1000		3828	19.92					
150.0800		1674	8.71					
151.0500		5336	27.77					
152.0800		1338	6.96					
153.1100		1098	5.71					
157.0600		1068	5.56					
159.0900		2561	13.32					
161.1100		4690	24.40					
162.1200		1203	6.26					
163.1100		4109	21.38					
165.0600		1178	6.13					
173.1100		2416	12.57					
175.1300		5196	27.04					
177.1100		2282	11.87					
187.1400		1841	9.58					
188.1500		1064	5.54					
189.1600		19218	100.00					
190.1600		6307	32.82					
191.1400		5011	26.07					
193.0600		1103	5.74					
201.1500		1160	6.04					
203.1600		4242	22.07					
204.1700		2285	11.89					
205.1300		1761	9.16					
207.0500	1	7226	37.60					
208.0500	1	1662	8.65					
218.1900		2082	10.83					

Analysis Report

Spectrum Peaks

m/z	Z	Abund	Abund %	m/z (Calc)	Diff (ppm)	Ion Species	Formula	Ion Type
229.2200		1295	6.74					
249.1600		1814	9.44					
253.0200		986	5.13					
281.0800		3386	17.62					
358.1600		1070	5.57					
408.3500		1348	7.01					
468.4400		1161	6.04					

Spectrum Identification Table

Best ID Source	Name	Formula	Species	m/z	Diff (ppm)	CAS	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (DB)	Score (MFG)	Lib/DB
Yes LibSearch	Solanesol	C45H74O				0-00-0	74.72	74.72			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Geranyl linalool isomer	C20H34O				0-00-0	72.59	72.59			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	2-(1-Hydroxymethylvinyl)-2-hydroxymethyl-3a,4-dimethylperhydroinden	C15H24O2				0-00-0	72.18	72.18			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	Geranyl linalool isomer B	C20H34O				0-00-0	68.56	68.56			W11N17main.L
No LibSearch	1-[3-(2,6,6-Trimethylcyclohex-2-enyl)-4,5-dihydro-3H-pyrazol-4-yl]-ethanone	C14H22N2O				997324-84-1	65.83	65.83			W11N17main.L

Best Name	Formula	m/z (prec.)	CAS	RT (DB)	RT Diff	Score	Score (Lib)	Score (Fwd)	Score (Rev)	Lib/DB
Yes Solanesol	C45H74O		0-00-0			74.72	74.72			W11N17main.L

Observed Spectrum

Mirror Plot

Library Spectrum

MassHunter Qual 10.0
(End of Report)